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**The future of precision orthodontics: Integration of
technology and biomedicine into customized therapy**

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سُبْحَانَكَ لَا عِلْمَ لَنَا إِلَّا مَا عَلَّمْتَنَا

إِنَّكَ أَنْتَ الْعَلِيمُ الْحَكِيمُ

صَدَقَ اللَّهُ الْعَظِيمُ

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

قسم الطبيب

أقسم بالله العظيم

أن أراقب الله في مهنتي...

و أن أصون حياة الإنسان في كافة أدوارها في كل الظروف والأحوال
بأذلا وسعي في استنقاذها من الهلاك و المرض و الألم والقلق.
و أن أحفظ للناس كرامتهم وأستر عورتهم و أكتم سرهم.
و أن أكون على الدوام من وسائل رحمة الله بأذلا رعايتي الطبية
للقريب و البعيد للصالح والخاطئ و الصديق و العدو.
و أن أثابر على طلب العلم أسخره لنفع الإنسان... لا لأذاه.
و أن أوقر من علمني و أعلم من يصغرنني وأكون لأخا لكل زميل في
المهنة الطبية متعاونين على البر و التقوى.
و أن تكون حياتي مصداق إيماني في سري و علانيتي نقية مما يشينها
تجاه الله و رسوله و المؤمنين.

و الله على ما أقول شهيد

Serment d'Hippocrate

En présence des maîtres de cette école, de mes chers condisciples, je promets et je jure d'être fidèle aux lois de l'honneur et de la probité dans l'exercice de la médecine.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AI: Artificial Intelligence

AJO-DO: American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics

ANN: Artificial Neural Network

AUC: Area Under the Curve

BN: Bayesian Network

BOA: Baseplates of Orthodontic Appliances

CCT: Controlled Clinical Trial

CFU: Colony Forming Units

CI: Confidence Interval

CNN: Convolutional Neural Network

CRD: Centre for Reviews and Dissemination

DOR: Diagnostic Odds Ratio

DTA: Diagnostic Test Accuracy

EBM: Evidence Based Medicine

EDI: Enamel Decalcification Index

FMDM: Faculty of Dental Medicine of Monastir

FN: False Negative

FP: False Positive

GRADE: Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation

ICC: Intraclass Correlation

ID: Identification

JI: Joanna Briggs Institute

L-PRF: Leukocyte and Platelet-Rich Fibrin

MA: Meta-analysis

ML: Machine Learning

NA: Not Applicable

NANO: Nanotechnology

NASEM: National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine

NBFG: Nano Bio-Fusion Gel

NLR: Negative Likelihood Ratio

NM: Not Mentioned

OCEBM: Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine

OTM: Orthodontic Tooth Movement

PAOO: Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics

PICOS: Population, Interventions, Comparators, Outcomes, Study Design

PLR: Positive Likelihood Ratio

PRF: Platelet-Rich Fibrin

PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

PRP: Platelet Rich Plasma

RCT: Randomized Controlled Trial

ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic

RT: Regenerative Therapy

SC: Stem Cells

Se: Sensitivity

Sp: Specificity

SR: Systematic Review

TN: True Negative

TP: True Positive

UCLP: Unilateral Cleft Lip and Palate

WHO: World Health Organisation

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Introduction

INTRODUCTION

Precision medicine or personalized medicine is an emerging medical management model that suggests the customization of healthcare, with clinical decisions, treatments, practices, and products being tailored to a subset of patients [101]. With its growing interest, progress in precision medicine foretells comparable advances in orthodontics and will be incrementally exploited to attain customized treatment approaches and amend treatment efficiencies.

In the 21st century, we are witnessing rapid progress in biomedicine, computer, and biomaterial technologies along with their potential applications in precision orthodontics [38].

In this review, the uprising of precision orthodontics will be investigated by analysing available literature about the emerging technologies and therapies that drive us closer to precise care: artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapy (Stem cells and Platelet-rich fibrin)[8,55,111].

In fact, with the use of artificial intelligence, expert systems for decision making and treatment planning that are specific to a subgroup of patients could be implemented. And thanks to nanotechnology, monitoring biological changes and precise treatments could be provided on the nanoscale. While with regenerative therapy, treatments that are customized to the patients' needs could be delivered thanks to the use of autologous cell transplants.

The following review will take the form of a systematic review, comprised of four parts. The first one will illustrate the review methodology. The second part will present the results. The third part will be a quantitative synthesis of the results through a meta-analysis. And lastly, the findings will be discussed along with providing recommendations for clinicians and future research.

Definition of terms

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the theory and development of computer systems that perform tasks usually requiring human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and language translation [39].

Nanotechnology (NANO) is the branch of technology concerned with dimensions and tolerances of less than 100 nanometres, particularly the manipulation of individual atoms and molecules [100].

Regenerative therapy (RT) is the process of replacing or "regenerating" human cells, tissues, or organs to recover or restore normal function. Stem cells and different blood products, primarily PRF, are the most commonly used regenerative products [99].

Stem cells (SC) are cells that have the potential to develop into a variety of different types of cells. They serve as a repair system for the body [113].

Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) is a second-generation platelet-rich plasma that contains autologous platelets and leukocytes in a complex fibrin matrix to accelerate the healing of soft and hard tissue [20].

Significance of the study

Artificial intelligence, nanotechnology and regenerative therapy constitute 3 of the main interests in the scientific community of this decade. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no research that investigated the milestones reached by these advancements in orthodontics. Hence, the need for a review that gathers all available evidence on the clinical use of these interventions, comparing them and determining which one of them has the current biggest impact and thus, proposing directions for future research.

Objectives

In this review, the aim was to collect, analyse and summarize all possible research available on the underlying review question, so that an assessment of the available evidence on the use of artificial intelligence, nanotechnology and regenerative therapy in the planning and delivery of an individual orthodontic treatment can be done. Furthermore, this review shall include an analysis of the implications of technology and biomedicine and their influence on contemporary orthodontic therapy. Based on that, follows an evaluation of the possibilities for modernizing the orthodontic practice and recommendations for clinicians and future research.

Materials and methods

1. Review question

This review was conducted in order to answer the following question: What is the impact of emerging technologies and therapies: artificial intelligence, nanotechnology and regenerative therapy (Stem cells and Platelet-rich fibrin), on contemporary orthodontics?

The present review was designed and reported conforming to the guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses: The (PRISMA) 2020 statement [66,67] and adhered to the Cochrane guidelines [14]. Approval for conducting this research was granted by the “Thesis committee” of the Faculty of Dental Medicine of Monastir (FMDM) in July 2021.

2. The PICO framework

Evidence based practice is defined as the conscientious, explicit, and judicious use of the best scientific evidence to support the clinical decision making. Identifying the best evidence requires the development of a well-built research question as well as a thorough review of the literature [72,78].

This concept of evidence-based medicine (EBM) recommends that clinicians formulate focused questions in terms of the population, intervention, comparison, and outcome. Together, these elements comprise a PICO framework. [35] This latter will serve as the frame and structure providing the major guidelines for this research. In this review, the PICO(S) variation was used detailed as follows:

- **P: Population**: Orthodontic patients, patients’ clinical images, radiographs, cephalograms.
- **I: Intervention**: Orthodontic treatment planning and delivery with artificial intelligence (AI), nanotechnology and regenerative therapy (Stem cells and Platelet-rich fibrin). The primary focus will be on interventions having a direct clinical significance and effects on the treatment outcome using those therapies and technologies.
- For AI: models assisting in treatment planning and decision making.
- For nanotechnology: nanotechnology applications in orthodontic treatment.

- For regenerative therapy: Stem cells and Platelet-rich fibrin applications in orthodontic treatment.
- **C: Comparison**: Reference standards, conventional treatments, therapeutic consensus.
- **O: Outcomes**: Effectiveness of the used technologies and therapies, and comparison of the evidence supporting each of the 3 interventions and their applications.

Depending on the main outcomes, it will be attempted to conduct a meta-analysis on the intervention having the most clinical significance and evidence concerning orthodontic practice. The meta-analysis would have these outcomes:

- Effectiveness of Nanotechnology for orthodontic treatment delivery.
- (OR) -Effectiveness of regenerative therapy for orthodontic treatment delivery.
- (OR) -Effectiveness and performance of AI models for orthodontic treatment planning and decision-making.
- **S: Study design**: Meta-analysis, systematic reviews, randomized controlled trial, controlled clinical trials, diagnostic test accuracy studies (DTA: single-gate/two-gate), case-control studies, retrospective and prospective cohorts.

Thus, the PICO form detailed research question was: What is the effectiveness of AI, nanotechnology and regenerative therapy in orthodontic treatment planning and delivery on orthodontic patients compared to conventional treatments?

3. The review team

The review team was composed of:

- A professor of orthodontics (ID).
- A thesis candidate in dental medicine and a former intern in the department of orthodontics at the University clinic of Dental Medicine of Monastir (JM).

Both team members worked independently yet synchronically on the following review by critical reading of articles, extraction and synthesis of data, and comparison of different outcomes and conclusions. Any disagreement between the

review team members was discussed and, if possible, resolved by consensus after referring to the protocol. However, if necessary, a third person was consulted.

4. Eligibility criteria for considering studies for this review

4.1. Inclusion criteria

- Articles must be based on artificial intelligence (AI), nanotechnology and regenerative therapy (stem cells and Platelet-rich fibrin).
(AI): will be defined as the self-reported use of AI, deep learning, machine learning, neural network, or any classifier prediction model.
- Articles should have a clinical significance in orthodontic interventions.
- There should be a mention of some measurable or predictive outcomes that can be quantified.
- Articles published from (1st January 2000) until (9th January 2021).
- Study design: Meta-analysis, systematic reviews, randomized controlled trial, controlled clinical trials, diagnostic test accuracy studies (DTA: single-gate/two-gate), case-control studies, retrospective and prospective cohorts.

4.2. Exclusion criteria

- Articles that focused on areas other than artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapy (stem cells and PRF).
- Articles that do not meet the purpose of the review.
- Articles with poor insufficient abstract data and whose full text was not available.
- Articles in languages other than English and French.
- Study design: Narrative reviews, case report, case series, animal studies, in vitro research reports, letters to the editors, commentaries, books, conferences.

5. Search strategy for identification of studies

5.1. Database search for published work

A combination of controlled vocabulary and medical subject headings (Mesh) terms was elaborated for identifying studies related to this review, which were adapted appropriately for each database to compensate for variations in syntax rules and vocabulary. For more pertinent refined results, the review team switched between Title, abstract and full text specified keywords (Appendix 1-A). The applied restrictions were the publication time and the study design as specified above.

According to the AMSTAR 2 guidelines, at least two databases should be searched in the SR/MA [16], but as the number of searched databases increases, much yield and more comprehensive, accurate results can be gained [80]. Therefore, the search for relevant studies included the following electronic databases:

- ✓ MEDLINE via PubMed
- ✓ EBSCO host (Dentistry & Oral Sciences Source database)
- ✓ ScienceDirect
- ✓ Scopus
- ✓ Web of Science (All databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO)

It should be noted that a 'catch-up' search will be executed if the interval since the initial bibliographic databases' search is greater than 12 months to update the review and identify recently relevant published articles [59].

From the 1st of January 2000 until the 9th of January 2021, the search results in the databases for each sub-topic were as follows (Appendix 1-B):

5.1.1. Artificial intelligence

- ❖ PubMed: 476 published works.
- ❖ EBSCO host: 60 published works.
- ❖ ScienceDirect: 95 published works.
- ❖ Scopus: 115 published works.
- ❖ Web of Science: 151 published works.

5.1.2. Nanotechnology

- ❖ PubMed: 392 published works.
- ❖ EBSCO host: 80 published works.
- ❖ ScienceDirect: 25 published works.
- ❖ Scopus: 94 published works.
- ❖ Web of Science: 112 published works.

5.1.3. Regenerative therapy (Stem cells / Platelet-rich fibrin)

- ❖ PubMed: 194 published works.
- ❖ EBSCO host: 52 published works.
- ❖ ScienceDirect: 32 published works.
- ❖ Scopus: 20 published works.
- ❖ Web of Science: 20 published works.

All records from the five databases mentioned previously have been collected and then imported into a single library of a citation manager “*EndNote™ 20*” [83] which assisted in combining the results obtained by all the searched databases and consequently allowed to discard duplicates automatically and keep records of the global search. Duplicates missed by *EndNote™20* were deleted manually.

Figure 1: EndNote™20 citation manager window

5.2. Additional search: Grey literature search/Hand searching

Identifying all evidence relevant to the research topic is an essential condition in conducting systematic reviews [65]. Hence, all possibilities to reduce bias, especially publication bias, by additional searching in electronic and non-electronic sources for published and unpublished work must be exhausted. The process was done as follows:

- Grey literature databases search: Open Grey / WorldCat.
- Hand-searching in non-electronic sources such as journals.
- Manual searching: scrutinizing references and citations from the included studies, contacting authors and experts, and looking at “related to” or “similar” articles in PubMed [80].

6. Data collection and analysis

6.1. Study selection

All articles from the EndNote library were divided into 3 groups based on the 3 different sub-interventions of interest (AI, NANO, STEM CELLS/PRF) and then exported to “*Rayyan QCRI*” which is an AI assisted systematic review web-tool designed to help researchers working on systematic reviews by speeding up the process of screening and selecting studies [64]. Rayyan will be used along with EndNote to record decisions.

Figure 2: Rayyan reviews interface

Complying with the University of York CRD’s guidance for undertaking reviews in health care [2], study selection was conducted in two stages by two reviewers independently:

- **Stage 1:** Initial screening of titles and abstracts of all studies against the predetermined inclusion criteria to identify potentially relevant papers. At this stage, it is important to be more inclusive than exclusive: if a definite decision for inclusion cannot be made based on the title and/or abstract alone due to inconclusiveness or in case of doubt, the studies were included for stage 2 assessment.
- **Stage 2:** Screening of the full papers identified as possibly relevant in the initial screening. Detailed full text assessment would discern which studies are eligible and which are to be excluded permanently.

Disagreements between the review team members were discussed, and resolved by consensus after referring to the protocol. Although, if deemed necessary, a third person was consulted.

All eligibility decisions were registered, and details of exclusion were recorded in the table of characteristics of excluded studies. The whole process was summarised in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 flow diagram [66].

6.2. Data extraction and management

A customized data collection form (Appendix 2) was designed for data extraction and was pilot-tested on six of the included studies (two studies of each sub-topic). This form was derived from the ones provided by the JBI manual for evidence synthesis [98] and the Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions [14] and it covered the following:

- Basic information of the study: study ID/ title / first author / journal...
- Study eligibility: all items listed in the inclusion criteria.
- Study details: aim / methods / population / results / outcomes...
- Summary of assessment table: final decision / contact of author / conclusions...

For AI, more data for extraction was added: the matter of investigation, type of diagnostic imaging or material, the type of AI approach, recruitment setting, clinical context, inclusion and exclusion criteria and outcomes (i.e. sensitivity, specificity, AUC).

The extraction of data was done independently by two reviewers, and then results were confronted, discussed, and revised together as a team.

➤ **Missing data request**

The authors of any studies found to have partial information were contacted by Email, and asked to provide the missing information.

6.3. Data synthesis

A qualitative synthesis of the included studies was provided, and the outcomes for each intervention were detailed and compared.

As for the quantitative synthesis, it was unclear whether the available body of evidence would allow the conduct of a meta-analysis. At the earlier stages of the project, a so-called "absence of evidence situation" could not be excluded, which would result in a descriptive manner of evidence synthesis. Thus, the quantitative analysis and synthesis were detailed in a separate section of the review.

7. Quality assessment

7.1. Assessment of the risk of bias in included studies

Two researchers independently assessed the risk of bias of the included articles using “**JBI critical appraisal tools**” [105] (Appendix 3). The purpose of this evaluation is to assess the study's methodological quality and to determine the extent to which a study has addressed the possibility of bias in its design, conduct and analysis.

Since this review includes several study designs, multiple JBI checklists were used depending on the study type (Appendix 3):

- ✓ Checklist for Systematic Reviews (11 parameters) [106]
- ✓ Checklist for Randomized Controlled Trials (13 parameters) [109]
- ✓ Checklist for Case Control Studies (10 parameters) [103]
- ✓ Checklist for Cohort Studies (11 parameters) [104]
- ✓ Checklist for Diagnostic Test Accuracy Studies (10 parameters) [107]
- ✓ Checklist for Quasi-experimental studies (9 parameters) [108]

The potential risk of bias was categorized as low if a study provided detailed information pertaining to 70% or more of the applicable parameters. Moderate risk was considered if a study provides information corresponding to less than 70% to 50% of the applicable parameters, whereas if a study showed missing information regarding more than 50% of the applicable parameters, the study was categorized as exhibiting a high risk of bias.

7.2. Levels of evidence

The “**2011 Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine (OCEBM) Levels of Evidence**” [32-34] (Appendix 4) was used to appraise the level of evidence in the included studies. This updated 2011 version attempts to provide a more comprehensive hierarchical grading for classifying scientific evidence based on study design. It defines 5 levels of evidence: Level 1 provides the strongest evidence for a recommendation. Level 5 designates the weakest evidence for each main review question.

7.3. Quality of evidence and strength of recommendations

For the evaluation of quality of evidence and strength of recommendations in each of the included studies, “**GRADE**” (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation) was used which is a framework currently emerging as the dominant systematic approach for appraising evidence and making recommendations for systematic reviews and guidelines in health care. It is endorsed by over 100 organizations, amongst others Cochrane, World Health Organization (WHO) and several guideline developers and institutions [9].

Decision regarding the strength of recommendations and quality of evidence was achieved by a consensus process whereby review team members assigned to each of the research questions considered the strength of the evidence using the GRADE methodology (table 1) (table 2) (Appendix 5).

Table 1: Strength of recommendation	
Strength	Description
1. Strong	Benefits clearly outweigh risks and burdens, or vice versa
2. Weak	Benefits closely balanced with risks and burdens

Table 2: Quality of evidence	
Quality	Description
A-High	Consistent evidence from well-performed randomized, controlled trials or overwhelming evidence of some other form; further research is unlikely to change our confidence in estimate of benefit and risks.
B-Moderate	Evidence from randomized, controlled trials with important limitations (inconsistent results, methodological flaws, indirect or imprecise), or very strong evidence of some other research design; further research (if performed) is likely to have impact on our confidence in estimate of benefit and risks and may change estimate
C-Low	Evidence from observational studies, unsystematic clinical experience, or randomized, controlled trials with serious flaws; any estimate of effect is uncertain

8. Review protocol registration

Early review protocol registration is highly recommended as it ensures transparency in the research process and protects against duplication issues. It also serves as a documented proof of the team's plan of action, research question, eligibility criteria, intervention, quality assessment, and pre-analysis plan. In the other hand, it allows for replication and updating, and to reduce the likelihood of selective reporting [80].

This review has been registered since 27th of February 2021 in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (**PROSPERO**) under the following registration number: **CRD42021230816** [112].

Results

1. Global selection process

The global search initially yielded 1918 records in total. All results were assigned to their respective sub-intervention group as follows:

- Artificial intelligence (AI): 897 results.
- Nanotechnology (NANO): 703 results.
- Regenerative therapy (SC/PRF): 318 results.

A sum of 585 duplicates (AI: 234, NANO: 247, SC/PRF: 104) were eliminated using the citation manager *EndNote™ 20*.

Therefore, for the first stage of study selection 1333 records (AI: 663, NANO: 456, SC/PRF: 214) were screened by titles and abstracts through *Rayyan*, discarding in the process 1298 articles (AI: 646, NANO: 449, SC/PRF: 203).

35 reports (AI: 17, NANO: 7, SC/PRF: 11) were sought for retrieval, from which, 1 article could not be retrieved (AI: 1) because of inaccessible full text.

Thus, at this stage, 34 reports had to be fully assessed for eligibility.

After meticulous reading and discussion, 24 (AI: 10, NANO: 6, SC/PRF: 8) included studies were identified and the remaining 10 (AI: 6, NANO: 1, SC/PRF: 3) articles were excluded.

A catch-up search was executed in the PubMed database on the 19th of January 2022 (from the 9th of January 2021 till the 19th of January 2022), using the same search query. This search yielded 219 records (AI: 140, NANO: 44, SC/PRF: 35). Only 4 articles made it to final inclusion (AI: 2, NANO: 2, SC/PRF: 0).

So, in the end, the final sample included 28 articles (AI: 12, NANO: 8, SC/PRF: 8).

Reasons for exclusion after full-text assessment are reported in the table of characteristics of excluded studies and the global selection process is illustrated, in accordance with the PRISMA guidelines, in the PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram [66].

Figure 3: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for AI [66]

Figure 4: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for nanotechnology studies [66]

Figure 5: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for regenerative therapy studies [66]

2. Description of Studies

2.1. Articles identification

The 28 (AI: 12, NANO: 8, STEM CELLS/PRF: 8) included papers underwent data extraction according to the predesigned data collection form. Basic information was collected to identify these articles: title, first author, journal, year of publication, study type, and the aim of study. All of which were reported in the following articles identification table. For each included article, a study ID was attributed, which is a unique code that combines the last name of the first author and the year of publication. The study ID was used to facilitate and simplify the article identification process for the review authors.

Table 3: Articles' identification

Study ID and Title	First author	Year	country	Study design	Journal	Aim of study
Artificial intelligence (AI) = 12 articles						
<u>Akcam 2002</u> [1] Fuzzy modelling for selecting headgear types	M. Okan Akcam	2002	Japan	DTA single gate case control	European Journal of orthodontics	To develop a computer-assisted inference model for selecting appropriate types of headgear appliance for orthodontic patients and to investigate its clinical versatility as a decision-making aid for inexperienced clinicians.
<u>Choi 2019</u> [13] Artificial intelligent model with neural network machine learning for the diagnosis of orthognathic surgery	Hyuk-II Choi	2019	Korea	DTA single gate case control	The journal of craniofacial surgery	To develop a new artificial intelligent model for surgery/non-surgery decision and extraction determination, and to evaluate the performance of this model.
<u>Jung 2016</u> [40] New approach for the diagnosis of extractions with neural network machine learning	Seok-Ki Jung	2016	Korea	DTA single gate case control	American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics	To construct an artificial intelligence expert system for the diagnosis of extractions using neural network machine learning and to evaluate the performance of this model.
<u>Khanagar 2020</u> [43] Scope and performance of artificial intelligence technology in orthodontic diagnosis, treatment planning, and clinical decision-making – A systematic review	Sanjeev B. Khanagar	2020	Saudi Arabia	Systematic review	Journal of dental sciences	To document the scope and performance of the artificial intelligence-based models that have been widely used in orthodontic diagnosis, treatment planning and predicting the prognosis.
<u>Kim 2021</u> [46] Influence of the depth of the convolutional neural networks on an artificial intelligence model for diagnosis of orthognathic surgery.	Ye-Hyun Kim	2021	Korea	DTA single gate case control	MDPI Journal of personalized medicine	To investigate the relationship between image patterns in cephalometric radiographs and the diagnosis of orthognathic surgery and propose a method to improve the accuracy of predictive models according to the depth of the neural networks.
<u>Li 2019</u> [48] Orthodontic treatment planning based on artificial neural networks	Peilin Li	2019	China	DTA single gate case control	Scientific reports	To use a multilayer perceptron artificial neural networks to predict orthodontic treatment plans, including the determination of extraction-nonextraction, extraction patterns, and anchorage patterns.

<p><u>Lin 2020</u> [50,51]</p> <p>Early prediction of the need for orthognathic surgery in patients with repaired unilateral cleft lip and palate using machine learning and longitudinal lateral cephalometric analysis data</p>	Guang Lin	2020	Korea	DTA single gate case control	<p>Thesis</p> <p>Reference published ahead of print 2020</p> <p>Article published in 2021 (The journal of craniofacial surgery)</p>	To determine the cephalometric parameters that can predict the future need for orthognathic surgery or distraction osteogenesis (DO) in Korean patients with repaired unilateral cleft lip and palate (UCLP) by using machine learning and longitudinal lateral cephalometric analysis.
<p><u>Nieri 2010</u> [62]</p> <p>Factors affecting the clinical approach to impacted maxillary canines: A Bayesian network analysis</p>	Michele Nieri	2010	USA	Retrospective cohort	American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics	To apply Bayesian networks to evaluate the relative role and possible causal relationships among various factors affecting the diagnosis and final treatment outcome of impacted maxillary canines.
<p><u>Shin 2021</u> [75]</p> <p>Deep learning based prediction of necessity for orthognathic surgery of skeletal malocclusion using cephalogram in Korean individuals.</p>	WooSang Shin	2021	Korea	DTA single gate case control	BMC oral health	To develop a deep learning network to automatically predict the need for orthognathic surgery using cephalogram.
<p><u>Suhail 2020</u> [77]</p> <p>Machine learning for the diagnosis of orthodontic extractions: A computational analysis using ensemble learning</p>	Yasir Suhail	2020	USA	DTA single gate case control	MDPI Bioengineering	To create an artificial intelligence decision-making model for the diagnosis of extractions using neural network machine learning.
<p><u>Thanathornwong 2018</u> [82]</p> <p>Bayesian-based decision support system for assessing the needs for orthodontic treatment</p>	Bhornawan Thanathornwong	2018	Thailand	DTA single gate cross sectional	Healthcare informatics research	To develop a clinical decision support system to help general practioners access the need for orthodontic treatment in patients with permanent dentition.
<p><u>Xie 2010</u> [91]</p> <p>Artificial neural network modelling for deciding if extractions are necessary prior to orthodontic treatment</p>	Xiaoqiu Xie	2010	China	DTA single gate case control	Angle Orthodontist	To construct a decision-making expert system (ES) for the orthodontic treatment of patients between 11 and 15 years old to determine whether extraction is needed by using artificial neural networks (ANN). Specifically, uncovering the factors that affect this decision-making process.

Nanotechnology (NANO) = 8 articles						
<u>Alam 2021</u> [3] Nano-Bio fusion gingival gel in the management of fixed orthodontic treatment-induced gingivitis: an empirical study	Mohammad Khurshheed Alam	2021	Saudi Arabia	triple-blind, split-mouth, prospective randomized controlled trial (RCT)	American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics	To investigate the effect of nano-bio fusion gingival gel (NBFG) in patients with malocclusion and undergoing fixed orthodontic treatment to control treatment-induced gingivitis and periodontitis.
<u>Ali 2021</u> [4] Effect of nanosilver mouthwash on prevention of white spot lesions in patients undergoing fixed orthodontic treatment- a randomized double-blind clinical trial	Azheeh Ali	2021	Iraq	Double-blind randomized controlled trial (RCT)	Journal of dental sciences	To investigate the varying effects of nano-silver, chlorhexidine or fluoride mouthwashes on white spot lesions.
<u>Badiee 2020</u> [7] Comparison of the effects of toothpastes containing nanohydroxyapatite and fluoride on white spot lesions in orthodontic patients: A randomized clinical trial	Mohammadreza Badiee	2020	Iran	Double-blind randomized controlled trial (RCT)	Dental research journal	To evaluate and compare the clinical effects of an Iranian toothpaste containing nano-hydroxyapatite (HA) with Fluoride (F) containing one on early enamel lesions.
<u>Farhadian 2016</u> [26] Streptococcus mutans counts in patients wearing removable retainers with silver nanoparticles vs those wearing conventional retainers: A randomized clinical trial	Nasrin Farhadian	2016	Iran	1:1 parallel 2-arm sex-matched, single-blind randomized clinical trial (RCT)	American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics	To evaluate the effect of adding silver nanoparticles to the acrylic baseplates of removable retainers of S. mutans colony-forming units in orthodontic patients.
<u>Ghorbanzadeh 2015</u> [29] Effects of baseplates of orthodontic appliances with in situ generated silver nanoparticles on cariogenic bacteria: A randomized, double-blind cross-over clinical trial	Roghayeh Ghorbanzadeh	2015	Iran	Double-blind randomized controlled clinical trial (RCT) with cross-over design	The journal of contemporary dental practice	To compare the clinical effectiveness of NanoAg in situ baseplates of orthodontic appliances (NanoAg-IS-BOA) and NanoAg incorporated BOA (NanoAg-I-BOA) to inhibition of planktonic growth and biofilm formation of the cariogenic bacteria.

<u>Jahanbin 2017</u> [36] A comparative assessment of enamel mineral content and streptococcus mutans population between conventional composites and composites containing nano amorphous calcium phosphate in fixed orthodontic patients: a split-mouth randomized clinical trial	Arezo Jahanbin	2017	Iran	Prospective, single-center, double-blind, split-mouth randomized controlled trial (RCT)	European journal of orthodontics	To evaluate the effect of the nano amorphous calcium phosphate (NACP) containing composite on enamel mineral contents and streptococcus mutans population in fixed orthodontic patients.
<u>Venkatesan 2020</u> [85] Evaluation of titanium dioxide coating on surface roughness of nickel-titanium archwires and its influence on streptococcus mutans adhesion and enamel mineralization: A prospective clinical study	Keerthi Venkatesan	2020	India	Prospective, split-mouth, controlled clinical trial (CCT)	American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics	To evaluate the effect of titanium dioxide (TiO ₂) coating on surface roughness (Ra) of nickel-titanium (NiTi) archwires and its influence on streptococcus mutans adhesion and enamel mineralization at the end of 1 month in orthodontic patients and to evaluate the integrity of the TiO ₂ coating.
<u>Wang 2012</u> [87] Clinical evaluation of remineralization potential of casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate nanocomplexes for enamel decalcification in orthodontics	Jun-Xiang Wang	2012	china	Controlled clinical trial (CCT)	Chinese medical journal	To evaluate the remineralizing effect of casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP) nanocomplexes on enamel decalcification in orthodontics.
Regenerative Therapy (STEM CELLS / PRF) = 8 articles						
<u>Dayoub 2019</u> [15] The role of platelet-rich fibrin in increasing the gingival thickness and modifying the thin gingival biotype: A comparative clinical split mouth study	Suleiman Dayoub	2019	Syria	Comparative split mouth randomized controlled trial (RCT)	Dental hypotheses	To evaluate the effectiveness of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) with tunnel flap compared to connective tissue graft (CTG) with tunnel flap in increasing gingival thickness (GTH) and reject the null hypothesis H ₀ (PRF has no effect in increasing GTH).
<u>Francisco 2020</u> [27] Platelet-rich fibrin in bone regenerative strategies in orthodontics: A systematic review	Inês Francisco	2020	Portugal	Systematic review	MDPI Materials	To investigate and appraise the quality of the most up to date available evidence from human studies regarding the applications and effects of PRF in orthodontics.

<p><u>Gonen 2019</u> [31]</p> <p>Evaluation of vestibular bone thickness in class I malocclusion treatment with corticotomy-assisted rapid orthodontics</p>	Zeynep Burcin Gonen	2019	Turkey	Randomized controlled trial (RCT)	The journal of craniofacial surgery	To evaluate the effects of corticotomy alone, corticotomy combined with bone graft, and corticotomy with platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) on vestibular bone thickness in patients with class I malocclusion. Then compare the treatment time with a conventional orthodontic therapy group. And investigate the periodontal health of patients who have undergone corticotomy-assisted rapid orthodontics.
<p><u>Mazzetti 2018</u> [56]</p> <p>Importance of stem cell transplantation in cleft lip and palate surgical treatment protocol</p>	Marcelo Paulo Vaccari	2018	Brazil	Prospective cohort	The journal of craniofacial surgery	To evaluate the effect of injection of stem cells from the umbilical cord, umbilical cord blood and placenta blood in surgical wound healing after primary lip and palate surgery in cleft lip and palate patients.
<p><u>Muñoz 2016</u> [60]</p> <p>Use of leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) in periodontally accelerated osteogenic orthodontics (PAOO): clinical effects on edema and pain</p>	Francisco Muñoz	2016	Chile	Prospective observational cohort	journal of clinical and experimental dentistry	To explore the clinical feasibility or effect of preparing and using L-PRF in PAOO in terms of post-operative inflammation, pain, infection, and short-term orthodontic stability.
<p><u>Nemtoi 2018</u> [61]</p> <p>The effect of a plasma with platelet-rich fibrin in bone regeneration and on rate of orthodontic tooth movement in adolescents</p>	Ana Nemtoi	2018	Romania	Split mouth, controlled clinical trial (CCT)	Revista de chimie	To evaluate the effect of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF), placed in extraction sockets, on bone regeneration and orthodontic tooth movement in adolescents.
<p><u>Pacheco 2020</u> [70]</p> <p>Distalization rate of maxillary canines in an alveolus filled with leukocyte-platelet-rich fibrin in adults: A randomized controlled clinical trial</p>	Ariel Adriano Reyes Pacheco	2020	Dominican Republic	Split mouth, randomized controlled trial (RCT)	American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics	To evaluate the Distalization rate and changes in inclination of the maxillary canines in alveoli preserved with (L-PRF) membranes in adult patients. The null hypothesis was that there are no differences in the canine distalization movement rate between the treated and the control sides.
<p><u>Tehranchi 2018</u> [81]</p> <p>The effect of autologous leukocyte platelet rich fibrin on the rate of orthodontic tooth movement: A prospective randomized clinical trial</p>	Azita Tehranchi	2018	Iran	Split mouth, randomized controlled trial (RCT)	European journal of dentistry	To evaluate the effect of L-PRF, placed in extraction sockets, on orthodontic tooth movement (OTM).

2.2. Design

For artificial intelligence studies: 10 studies were diagnostic test accuracy studies (DTA); from which 9 had single-gate case control design and 1 study had a single-gate cross sectional design. 1 study was a systematic review and 1 study a retrospective cohort.

For nanotechnology studies: 6 studies were randomized controlled trials (RCT); from which 1 study had a cross-over design and 2 other studies had a split-mouth design. The remaining 2 studies were controlled clinical trials, one of which had a split-mouth design.

For regenerative therapy studies: 4 studies were randomized controlled trials (RCT); from which 3 had split-mouth design. 2 studies were prospective cohorts, 1 was a controlled clinical trial with a split-mouth design and 1 was a systematic review.

Figure 6: Study design proportions

2.3. Setting

The included studies took place in 16 different countries with 5 trials conducted in Iran and Korea, both behold the highest number across studies. China came in second place with 3 studies. Two trials were conducted in the United States of America and Saudi Arabia, and one trial in each of Thailand, Japan, India, Iraq, Syria, Portugal, Turkey, Chile, Romania, Dominican Republic, and Brazil.

2.4. Identification site or journal

All included studies were published trials and 18 different journals in total were identified. The distribution of total papers according to the publishing journal was as follows: six articles from the AJO-DO, four from the journal of craniofacial surgery (including one thesis which was published as an article in 2021 at this journal), two articles from the European Journal of Orthodontics and Journal of dental sciences, and lastly one article from each of the remaining Journals (Scientific reports, MDPI Materials, MDPI Bioengineering, MDPI personalized medicine, BMC oral health, Healthcare informatics research, Angle Orthodontist, Dental research journal, The journal of contemporary dental practice, Chinese medical journal, Dental hypotheses, journal of clinical and experimental dentistry, Revista de chimie, European journal of dentistry).

2.5. Period of study

Studies were collected with publication dates ranging from 2002 to 2021. Seven out of the included trials were published in 2020. It is noticeable that there is an ascending trend concerning this review's three main topics (Artificial intelligence, Nanotechnology, Regenerative therapy: stem cells and PRF) which translates to a growing interest of the scientific community by these interventions.

Figure 7: Distribution of included trials per intervention according to the period of study

3. Risk of bias in included studies

The risk of bias assessment was done using JBI Critical Appraisal Checklists corresponding to each study design/type present in the included articles:

- ✓ Checklist for Systematic Reviews (11 parameters)
- ✓ Checklist for Randomized Controlled Trials (13 parameters)
- ✓ Checklist for Cohort Studies (11 parameters)
- ✓ Checklist for Diagnostic Test Accuracy Studies (10 parameters)
- ✓ Checklist for Quasi-experimental studies: non-randomized trials (9 parameters)

The Checklist for Case Control Studies was not used as this review did not identify any study that had a case control design.

Details on the risk of bias assessment for each study as well as the assessment grades are reported in the following table.

Artificial intelligence articles risk of bias assessment														
Study ID	Checklist	Checklist for diagnostic test accuracy studies										Assessment		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10			
Akçam 2002 [1]		U	N	U	N	U	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	40%	-	
Choi 2019 [13]		U	N	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	60%	=	
Jung 2016 [40]		U	N	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	60%	=	
Kim 2021 [46]		U	N	U	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	60%	=	
Li 2019 [48]		U	N	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	60%	=	
Lin 2020 [50]		U	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	70%	+	
Shin 2021 [75]		Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	80%	+	
Suhail 2020 [77]		U	N	Y	N	U	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	50%	=	
Thanathornwong 2018 [82]		U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	90%	+	
Xie 2010 [91]		U	N	Y	N	Y	U	Y	NA	U	Y	44.4%	-	
		Checklist for cohort studies												
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11		
Nieri 2010 [62]		NA	NA	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	NA	Y	75%	+
		Checklist for systematic reviews												
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11		
Khanagar 2020 [43]		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	NA	Y	U	80%	+

Nanotechnology articles risk of bias assessment																
Study ID	Checklist	Checklist for randomized controlled trials (RCT)												Assessment		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12			Q13
Alam 2021 [3]		Y	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	76.9%	+
Ali 2021 [4]		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	92.3%	+
Badiee 2020 [7]		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	84.6%	+
Farhadian 2016 [26]		Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	84.6%	+
Ghorbanzadeh 2015 [29]		U	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	61.5%	=
Jahanbin 2017 [36]		Y	NA	NA	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	90.9%	+
Regenerative therapy (SC/PRF) articles risk of bias assessment																
Study ID	Checklist	Checklist for cohort studies												Assessment		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11				
Muñoz 2016 [60]		NA	NA	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	NA	Y	62.5%	=		
Mazzetti 2018 [56]		Y	Y	Y	U	U	Y	N	Y	U	U	Y	54.6%	=		
Regenerative therapy (SC/PRF) articles risk of bias assessment																
Study ID	Checklist	Checklist for systematic reviews												Assessment		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11				
Francisco 2020 [27]		Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	NA	Y	Y	100%	+	
Regenerative therapy (SC/PRF) articles risk of bias assessment																
Study ID	Checklist	Checklist for randomized controlled trials (RCT)												Assessment		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12			Q13
Dayoub 2019 [15]		Y	NA	NA	U	U	U	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	63.6%	=
Gonen 2019 [31]		U	U	U	U	N	N	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	46.2%	-
Pacheco 2020 [70]		Y	NA	NA	N	N	U	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	63.6%	=
Tehranchi 2018 [81]		Y	NA	NA	U	U	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	72.7%	+
Regenerative therapy (SC/PRF) articles risk of bias assessment																
Study ID	Checklist	Checklist for quasi-experimental studies: controlled trials (CCT)												Assessment		
		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9						
Nemtoi 2018 [60]		Y	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	77.8%	+			

Table 4: Assessment of the risk of bias in included studies

+ Low risk - High risk = Moderate risk

Y: yes N: no U: unclear NA: not applicable

4. Level and Quality of evidence / strength of recommendations

After risk of bias assessment of the included articles, the study design, study quality, imprecision, indirectness, inconsistency, applicability, and effect size in each study was further evaluated. The 2011 OCEBM levels of evidence was used [33] and levels were graded down (↓) if any concerns about the aforementioned points occurred.

GRADE recommendations [9] were attributed to the concerned studies by an adapted consensual process after evaluation of the previously mentioned factors in addition to the estimate of benefits and risks and methodological flaws.

Table 5: OCEBM levels of evidence and GRADE recommendations across studies

Study ID	OCEBM	GRADE	Study ID	OCEBM	GRADE
Artificial intelligence			Nanotechnology		
Akçam 2002 [1]	4	1-C	Alam 2021 [3]	2	1-B
Choi 2019 [13]	4	1-C	Ali 2021 [4]	2	1-A
Jung 2016 [40]	4	1-C	Badiee 2020 [7]	2	1-B
Khanagar 2020 [43]	1	1-B	Farhadian 2016 [26]	2	1-A
Kim 2021 [46]	4	1-C	Ghorbanzadeh 2015 [29]	3↓	1-B
Li 2019 [48]	4	1-C	Jahanbin 2017 [36]	2	1-A
Lin 2020 [50]	4	1-C	Venkatesan 2020 [85]	3	1-C
Nieri 2010 [62]	4	1-C	Wang 2012 [87]	3	1-C
Shin 2021 [75]	4	1-C	Regenerative therapy		
Suhail 2020 [77]	4	1-C	Dayoub 2019 [15]	3↓	1-B
Thanathornwong 2018 [82]	2	1-C	Francisco 2020 [27]	1	1-B
Xie 2010 [91]	4	1-C	Gonen 2019 [31]	3↓	1-B
Regenerative therapy			Muñoz 2016 [60]	3	1-C
Tehranchi 2018 [81]	3↓	2-B	Nemtoi 2018 [61]	3	1-B
Mazzetti 2018 [56]	3	1-C	Pacheco 2020 [70]	3↓	1-B

5. Data extraction and synthesis

5.1. Excluded studies

A sum of 1894 articles were excluded during the selection process as follows:

- 585 (AI: 234, NANO: 247, SC/PRF: 104) discarded duplicates (*EndNote™ 20*)
- 1298 (AI: 646, NANO: 449, SC/PRF: 203) excluded articles after the title and abstract screening process.
- 1 (AI: 1) discarded article owing to inaccessible full-text [63].
- 10 (AI: 6, NANO: 1, SC/PRF: 3) excluded articles during the eligibility process. These articles have been discarded following their in-depth critical reading and the reasons for exclusion are detailed in the following table.

A total of 215 articles from the catch-up search were excluded:

- 210 (AI: 137, NANO: 40, SC/PRF: 33) excluded articles after the title and abstract screening process.
- 3 (NANO: 2, SC/PRF: 1) excluded article due to inaccessible full-text.
- 2 (AI: 1, NANO: 0, SC/PRF: 1) excluded articles during the eligibility process.

Table 6: Characteristics of excluded studies

Number	Title	First Author	Year	Reasons for exclusion
Artificial intelligence (7 excluded articles)				
1	Decision-making system for orthodontic treatment planning based on direct implementation of expertise knowledge [92]	Masakazu Yagi	2010	Conference paper
2	Prediction of class III treatment outcomes through orthodontic data mining [6]	Pietro Auconi	2015	Prognosis/Prevalence study
3	Artificial intelligence expert systems with neural network machine learning may assist decision-making for extractions in orthodontic treatment planning [79]	Kenji Takada	2016	Article commentary
4	Computer-aided heuristics in orthodontics [5]	Pietro Auconi	2020	Prognosis study

5	The impacts of orthognathic surgery on the facial appearance and age perception of patients presenting skeletal class III deformity: An outcome study using the FACE-Q report and surgical professional-based panel assessment [18]	Rafael Denadai	2020	Not relevant to our subject (not treatment planning or decision-making intervention)
6	iOrthoPredictor: Model-guided deep prediction of teeth alignment [93]	Lingchen Yang	2020	Not relevant to our subject (image segmentation)
7	Evaluation of the efficiency of computerized algorithms to formulate a decision support system for deepbite treatment planning [24]	Mostafa M. El-Dawaltly	2021	Not a classifier prediction model
Nanotechnology (1 excluded articles)				
8	A various soft tissue evaluation of the patients treated by nanocoating orthodontic arch-wires: perceptions in lateral profile photographs and lateral cephalometric radiographs [41]	Nazli Idil Kacamak	2020	Not relevant to our subject (NB: the article was retracted on August 2021 by the editor-in-chief and the publisher [42])
Regenerative therapy: Stem cells/PRF (4 excluded articles)				
11	Bioglass in alveolar bone regeneration in orthodontic patients: Randomized controlled trial [23]	N. El Shazley	2016	Not relevant to our subject (No direct application of PRF or stem cells)
9	Alveolar cleft reconstruction using different grafting techniques [58]	Aida Mossaad	2019	Not orthodontic patients
10	Coronally advanced flap with and without platelet-rich-fibrin in the treatment of multiple adjacent recession defects: A randomized controlled split-mouth trial [69]	Anudhree Manohar Potey	2019	Not relevant to our subject (Not orthodontic intervention)
12	Effectiveness of platelet rich fibrin versus demineralized bone xenograft in periodontally accelerated osteogenic orthodontics: a pilot comparative clinical study [94]	Aniruddh Yashwant V	2021	No conventional treatment comparison

5.2. Included Studies

The data from the 28 clinical studies was extracted using the pre-designed data collection form (Appendix 2), and the different PICO elements for each study were assembled. The following table contains the gathered information on epidemiological and clinical data (Table 7).

Table 7: Epidemiological and clinical data of included trials

Study ID	Participants / Follow-up			interventions	comparison	Outcomes/Results	conclusions
	Number	Age	Gender				
Nanotechnology (NANO) = 8 articles							
Alam 2021 [3]	32 (split-mouth): -32 intervention group -32 control group	<u>Age range:</u> [15;25] years	NM	Application of NBFG on the experimental side, twice a day after brushing for 90 days.	Application of placebo gel on control side.	<u>the plaque index (PI), papillary bleeding gingival index (PBI), probing depth (PD), and clinical attachment loss (CAL):</u> From baseline to the seventh day to the 90th day, the treatment group showed significant improvement in PI, PBI, and PD over time compared with the placebo group ($P<0.001$).	NBFG demonstrated a beneficial clinical effect in a relatively short period. NBFG, with its own beneficial modalities, allows us to advocate in the management of fixed orthodontic treatment induced gingivitis.
	<u>Follow-up:</u> 90 days (3 months)						
Ali 2021 [4]	42 (no drop-outs): -Group 1: 14 -Group 2: 14 -Group 3: 14	<u>Age range:</u> [18;37] years <u>Mean age:</u> 23.02 ± 3.841	<u>Males:</u> 16 <u>Females:</u> 26	-Group 1: nanosilver mouthwash -Group 2: chlorhexidine mouthwash -Group 3: fluoride mouthwash	Inter-group comparison	<u>White spot lesion extent (naked eye method):</u> There is significant difference in white spot lesions formation between the three groups; the mean of WSLs in nanosilver group is lower than CHX and fluoride group in 90 and 180 days of follow-up ($P<0.05$).	Nano-silver mouthwash is more effective than CHX and fluoride mouthwash in reducing WSLs during orthodontic treatment.
	<u>Follow-up:</u> 180 days (6 months)						
Badiie 2020 [7]	50 (no drop-outs): -25 intervention group -25 control group	<u>Age range:</u> [10;35] years	<u>Males:</u> 17 <u>Females:</u> 33	Nano-Hydroxyapatite toothpaste vs fluoride toothpaste use in fixed orthodontic patients after debonding.	Fluoride toothpaste	<u>White spot lesion extent and degree of remineralization:</u> -White spot lesion degree -Fluorescence value (DIAGNOdent) -Photography analysis -Plaque index ▪ Lesion extent showed a significant decrease ($P<0.001$).	-Nano-HA containing toothpaste performs better than F containing toothpaste in terms of remineralization -Age and gender do not affect the remineralizing potential -During 6-month period, both agents resulted in improved remineralization, while nano-HA preforms better -Nano-Ha containing toothpaste is an appropriate method of controlling early enamel lesions
	<u>Follow-up:</u> 6 months						

Farhadian 2016 [26]	<p>66 (5 drop-outs): -33 intervention group (1 drop-out: missed follow-up) -33 control group (4 drop-outs: missed follow-up/poor cooperation) Follow-up: 7 weeks</p>	<p><u>Mean age (intervention):</u> 17.8 years</p> <p><u>Mean age (control):</u> 16.3 years</p>	<p><u>-Intervention group:</u> M:11/F: 22</p> <p><u>-Control group:</u> M:10/F:23</p>	<p>Silver nanoparticles removable retainers use during the retention period in patients who completed their fixed orthodontic treatment and needed removable appliances as retainers.</p>	<p>Conventional removable retainers</p>	<p>- <u>The antibacterial effect of nanosilver in the acrylic baseplates (digital colony counter):</u> -Number of S mutans colony forming units (CFU) after 7 weeks of retainer use (Digital colony counter) -comparison of S. mutans count at T1(7 days after debonding) and T2(7 weeks after retainer delivery) in both control and intervention groups: Intervention: T1=58.84 , T2=33.0 / Control: T1=64.34 , T2=73.3 / P value at T2 < 0.001</p>	<p>Silver nanoparticles incorporated into the acrylic plate of retainers with 500 ppm concentration and 40 nm in size had a strong antimicrobial effect against S. mutans colony forming units under clinical conditions.</p>
Ghorbanzadeh 2015 [29]	<p>24 Follow-up: 16 weeks (4 months)</p>	<p><u>Mean age:</u> 12.6 years</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [7;15] years</p>	<p><u>Males:</u> 9 <u>Females:</u> 15</p>	<p>2 experimental BOA: NanoAg in situ baseplates of orthodontic appliances (NanoAg-IS-BOA) and NanoAg incorporated BOA (NanoAg-I-BOA) use in patients needing a treatment with removable orthodontic appliances.</p>	<p>Control BOA with Standard PMMA (Polymethyl-meth-acrylate)</p>	<p>- <u>Inhibition of planktonic growth and biofilm formation of the cariogenic bacteria (S.mutans/S.sobrinus/L.acidophilus/L.casei):</u> *Planktonic growth of the cariogenic bacteria (log10 CFU/ml in saliva samples) *Biofilm formation of the cariogenic bacteria (membrane-filter technique: log10 CFU/ml adhering to BOA) *The average levels of test cariogenic bacteria in saliva decreased about 2 to 70-fold compared to baseline depending on the microorganism and test BOA. *NanoAg-IS-BOA and NanoAg-I-BOA inhibited the biofilm of all test bacteria by 20.1% to 79.9% compared to BOA.</p>	<p>-NanoAg-IS-BOA and NanoAg-I-BOA showed a higher bacterial inhibitory activity than untreated BOA. -NanoAg-IS-BOA has strong antimicrobial activity in the planktonic phase and subsequent biofilm formation of cariogenic bacteria than NanoAg-I-BOA. -Wearing NanoAg-IS-BOA has the potential to minimize plaque formation of cariogenic bacteria and dental caries.</p>
Jahanbin 2017 [36]	<p>25 (5 drop-outs: -4 lost to follow-up -1 discontinued intervention) 20 teeth in each control and test group Follow-up: 6 months</p>	<p><u>Mean age:</u> 15.5 years</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [13;18] years</p>	<p><u>Males:</u> 0 <u>Females:</u> 25</p>	<p>Nano amorphous calcium phosphate (NACP) containing composite (Transbond XT 5% NACP) use for bonding in patients needing fixed orthodontic treatment.</p>	<p>Orthodontic composite (Transbond XT) without NACP</p>	<p>- <u>Count of S. mutans population around the lateral incisor and second premolars brackets (real-time PCR):</u> In the 3rd and 6th month, the bacterial population was significantly lower in the study side than the control side (P=0.01 and 0.000). - <u>The enamel mineral content of the lateral and second premolar teeth in both groups (fluorescence):</u> In the 6th month, mineral content on the study side was significantly higher than the controls (P=0.004).</p>	<p>The NACP-containing bonding agent was able to reduce the amount of cariogenic bacteria around the bracket and was able to prevent enamel mineral content reduction over a long term.</p>

Venkatesan 2020 [85]	12 patients (24 arches)	<u>Age range:</u> [14;25] years	NM	Titanium dioxide (TiO ₂) nanoparticle coated nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) archwires used in patients who were to undergo orthodontic treatment with fixed appliance (n=12).	Uncoated Ni-Ti archwires (n=12)	<p>- <u>Surface roughness (Ra) (3D surface profilometry):</u> After 1 month, both coated and uncoated archwires had a rougher surface, with coated ones demonstrating a greater increase.</p> <p>- <u>S. mutans adhesion (real-time PCR)</u> Coated wires demonstrated lower S. mutans adhesion compared to uncoated wires.</p> <p>- <u>Enamel mineralization (fluorescence DIAGNOdent)</u> No significant difference.</p> <p>- <u>Surface topography (scanning electron microscopy):</u> the coating showed delamination, deterioration and was lost by 60% at the end of 1 month.</p>	<p>-TiO₂ nanoparticle coating on NiTi archwires causes an initial reduction in roughness; however, at the end of 1 month, the benefit was lost.</p> <p>-S. mutans adhesion was lesser on the coated wires, which could be attributed to reduced initial Ra and antibacterial property of TiO₂.</p> <p>-Orthodontic archwires appears to have a limited role in enamel demineralization.</p>
	<u>Follow-up:</u> 1 month						
Wang 2012 [87]	40 (no drop-outs): -Intervention group: 20 -Control group: 20	<u>Mean age:</u> -intervention: 14 years -control: 16 years	<u>Intervention group:</u> M:12/F:8 <u>-Control group:</u> M:10/F:10	GC Tooth Mousse containing Casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP) nanocomplexes use in orthodontic patients.	Fluoride toothpaste 1100 ppm	<p><u>Remineralization potential of CPP-ACP for enamel decalcification:</u></p> <p>- Intraoral images</p> <p>- Enamel decalcification index (EDI): The mean EDI decreased significantly ($P < 0.01$) after using Tooth Mousse over the six-month study period. The mean EDI of control group had no significant difference before and after treatment.</p>	CPP-ACP can effectively improve the demineralized enamel lesions during orthodontic treatment, so it has some remineralization potential for enamel decalcification in orthodontics.
	<u>Follow-up:</u> 6 months						
Regenerative Therapy (STEM CELLS / PRF) = 8 articles							
Dayoub 2019 [15]	<u>22 (2 drop-outs):</u> -2 lost to follow-up	<u>Mean age:</u> 27 years	<u>Males:</u> 9 <u>Females:</u> 13	Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) with tunnel flap to modify thin gingival biotype (GBT) and increase gingival thickness (GTH) for patients at first or last stage of fixed orthodontic treatment (n=20).	Connective tissue graft (CTG) with tunnel flap (n=20)	<p>- <u>Gingival thickness (GTH):</u> The mean GTH at 6 months was 1.57 and 1.64mm for test and control group.</p> <p>- <u>Gingival biotype (GBT):</u> All 40 thin biotypes became thick after 6 months.</p> <p>- <u>Width of keratinized gingiva (WKG):</u> The gain of WKG was 1.57 and 2.08mm in test and control sites</p> <p>*No statistical differences were found between the two groups ($P > 0.05$).</p>	<p>-PRF has an effect in increasing GTH.</p> <p>-Both surgical techniques increased the GTH, and all the thin biotypes became thick after 6 months of the surgery.</p> <p>-Using PRF seemed to be a successful treatment option for thin GBT and it could serve as an alternative to CTG.</p>
	<u>Follow-up:</u> 6 months						

Francisco 2020 [27]	<p>-<u>alveolar cleft reconstruction</u>: (6 studies) Total population: 136</p> <p>-<u>Tooth movement and post-orthodontic stability</u>: (3 studies) Total population: 39</p>	6 to 51 years of age.	-	Participants who underwent treatments approaches with the use of PRF with/without a combined biomaterial.	The control group consisted of participants that underwent treatments approaches without PRF.	<p>- <u>Hard tissue reconstruction of alveolar bone</u>: Assessed by volume of the newly formed bone (measured in cubic centimetre or percentage of newly formed bone).</p> <p>- <u>Rate of orthodontic tooth movement</u>: Assessed by the change in horizontal linear distance between the mid-marginal ridges of the adjacent teeth (measured in millimetres).</p>	<p>-Despite the limitations in the included studies, this systematic review suggested that PRF can improve alveolar cleft reconstruction.</p> <p>-Concerning orthodontic tooth movement, the results highlight the positive effects of PRF, since it may shorten the orthodontic treatment time, thereby reducing associated costs.</p> <p>-Further, high-quality randomized controlled trials with identical methodologies, larger sample size, and longer follow-up periods are required.</p>
Gonen 2019 [31]	<p><u>30 (no drop-outs)</u>: -Group 1: 10 -Group 2: 10 -Group 3: 10</p>	<p><u>Mean age</u>: (years) -Group 1: 15.1 -Group 2: 15 -Group 3: 15.4</p>	<p>-Group 1: M:2/F:8 -Group 2: M:1/F:9 -Group 3: M:3/F:7</p>	<p>Speeding up orthodontic treatment with corticotomy-assisted rapid orthodontics: -corticotomy alone (1) -corticotomy with bone graft (2) -corticotomy with PRF (3)</p>	<p>-Inter-group comparison -Historic control group records of 30 patients with class I and moderate crowding that received conventional orthodontic treatment.</p>	<p>- <u>Duration of orthodontic treatment</u>: The mean duration of treatment was significantly different between the corticotomy patients (11 months) and the historic group patients (27.3 months) ($P=0.00$).</p> <p>- <u>Vestibular bone thickness (CBCT)</u>: In upper arch: all methods increased thickness. In lower arch: group 1 had bone loss Group 2 had the greatest increase in vestibular bone thickness.</p> <p>- <u>Periodontal assessments</u>: The width of keratinized gingiva decreased in groups 1 and 2, while no change was observed in group 3.</p>	<p>-Corticotomy-assisted rapid orthodontics decreased treatment times.</p> <p>-Sufficient alveolar bone thickness and preservation of the periodontal health were achieved when the corticotomy procedure was either combined with a bone graft or with PRF in class I malocclusion patients.</p> <p>-Bone grafts provided better bone thickness at the buccal surface of the anterior teeth of the mandible and maxilla, whereas the thickness of keratinized gingiva was better with PRF.</p> <p>-Combined corticotomy-PRF approach does not cause any decrease in the width of keratinized gingiva over time while providing bone thickness.</p>
Muñoz 2016 [60]	<p><u>11 (no drop-outs)</u></p>	<p><u>Mean age</u>: 34.8 years</p> <p><u>Age range</u>: [15;51] years</p>	<p>Males: 3 Females: 8</p>	<p>A Wicklo's modified periodontally accelerated osteogenic orthodontics (PAOO) technique with L-PRF incorporated into the graft and as covering membrane.</p>	NM	<p>- <u>Pain / post-surgical inflammation and infection (clinical parameters and patient feedback)</u>: Accelerated wound healing with no signs of infection or adverse reactions was evident.</p> <p>- <u>Short-term orthodontic stability (rigid night guard splints)</u>: The average orthodontic treatment time was 9.3 months. All cases were deemed stable for 2 years.</p>	<p>L-PRF is simple and safe to use in PAOO. Combination with traditional bone grafts potentially accelerates wound healing and reduces post-surgical pain, inflammation, infection without interfering with tooth movement and/or post-orthodontic stability, over a 2 years period; thus, alleviating the need for analgesics and anti-inflammatory medications.</p>

Nemtoi 2018 [61]	20 patients (40 extraction sockets)	<p><u>Mean age:</u> 16.43 years</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [12;20] years</p>	Males: 9 Females: 11	Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) placed in extraction sockets (n=20)	Extraction sockets with secondary healing (n=20)	<p>-<u>Bone regeneration (CBCT)/ bone healing (bone density in Hounsfield unit):</u> Improvement of bone regeneration in patients who received PRF. Presence of significant correlations between bone quality and socket augmentation with PRF.</p> <p>-<u>Orthodontic tooth movement (horizontal linear distance between the mid-marginal ridges of the adjacent teeth):</u> The experimental group which received PRF graft showed higher rate of OTM ($P=0.006$).</p>	<p>-PRF can be used as an inexpensive autologous material for socket preservation and future rehabilitation.</p> <p>-PRF may accelerate orthodontic tooth movement, particularly in cases with extraction treatment plan.</p>
	Follow-up: 24 weeks (6 months)						
Pacheco 2020 [70]	<p><u>21 (4 drop-outs:</u> -1 pregnant -1 gave-up -1 periodontal problems -1 went to study abroad) Each patient has 2 sides (control/test)</p>	<p><u>Mean age:</u> 33 ± 5.9 years</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [20;45] years</p>	Males: 5 Females: 12	Alveolus filled with L-PRF after first premolar extraction (n=17)	Alveolus without alveolar preservation treatment (n=17)	<p>- <u>Rate of distalization of the maxillary canines</u> (monthly measurement with a flexible ruler).</p> <p>- <u>Canine inclination</u> (CBCT scans) The distalization rate and inclination of the canines were greater on the control side than on the side treated with L-PRF ($P<0.05$). A weak correlation was found between the distalization rate and inclination of the canines for both sides (control side, $\rho=0.17$; experimental, $\rho=0.11$)</p>	<p>-The use of L-PRF in young adult patients decreased the rate of distalization and changes in inclination of the maxillary canines compared with the control group.</p> <p>-The use of L-PRF together with orthodontic treatment should be reconsidered.</p>
	Follow-up: 5 months						
Tehranchi 2018 [81]	8 patients (30 extraction sockets)	<p><u>Mean age:</u> 17.37 ± 12.48 years</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [12;25] years</p>	Males: 5 Females: 3	Application of L-PRF in tooth extraction sockets (n=15)	Extraction sockets with secondary healing (n=15)	<p>- <u>Orthodontic tooth movement</u> (measured by comparing the change in horizontal linear distance between the mid-marginal ridges of the adjacent teeth on a regular basis every 2 weeks for 4 months by digital caliper): A statistically significant difference was found between the experimental and control group in rate of OTM ($P=0.006$).</p>	Application of L-PRF as an interdisciplinary approach combining orthodontics and surgery, may accelerate OTM, particularly in extraction cases.
	Follow-up: 16 weeks (4 months)						
Mazzetti 2018 [56]	18 -intervention group: stem cell group (SCG): 9 -control group (CG): 9	<p><u>Mean age:</u> 5.11 months</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [4;6] months</p>	-SCG: M:4/F:5 -CG: M:4/F:5	Injection of stem cells in surgical wound after primary lip and palate surgery in cleft lip and palate patients (n=9)	Conventional surgical procedure without stem cells (n=9)	<p>- <u>Lip soft tissue inflammatory process in first 48h</u></p> <p>- <u>Lip transitory hypertrophic scar (2-6 months)</u></p> <p>- <u>Palatal dehiscence</u></p> <p>- <u>Palatal fistula</u></p>	<p>-The SCG had less inflammatory response at lip soft tissue, less scar hypertrophy, no palate fistula or dehiscence and less fibrosis between hard and soft palate at the second palatal surgery.</p> <p>-No evidence of bone neoformation.</p>

						<p>- <u>Fibrosis between soft and hard palate at the second surgical time</u> Outcomes were assessed by clinical subjective graduation (visual aspect / finger sensitivity): No surgical complications at SCG, all patients presented a good scar aspect and little inflammatory process. None presented dehiscence. The SCG presented higher percentage of "negative" classification in soft tissue inflammatory process ($P=0.001$), transitory hypertrophy scar ($P<0.001$), fibrosis between hard and soft palate ($P<0.001$)</p>
<p><u>Follow-up:</u> 10 years</p>						
<p>NB: Both groups of patients were submitted to orthopedic treatment with palatal device since their birth.</p>						

Artificial intelligence (AI) = 12 articles

Study ID	Population (Sample)	Intervention			comparison	Evaluation	Results/Outcomes (+) effective, (-) non effective, (N) neutral	Conclusions
		Study factor	Modality	AI approach				
Akçam 2002 [1]	<p>85 orthodontic patients' pre-treatment records <u>Mean age:</u> 12.9±4.6 years <u>Age range:</u> [8.1;31.1] years <u>Males:</u> 33 <u>Females:</u> 52</p>	<p>Headgear type: -Low -Medium -High pull</p>	<p>-Dental casts -Intra and extra-oral photographs -Panoramic radiographs -Lateral cephalograms</p>	<p>Fuzzy modelling</p>	<p>8 experienced orthodontists (6 men, 2 women) <u>Experience:</u> -Mean: 14.7±3.7 years -Range: [10.1;20.9] years</p>	<p>Average satisfaction was 95.6% (SD 2.6)</p>	<p>(+) effective -All of the examiners exceeded a kappa score of 0.7, allowing them to evaluate the inference model -The examiners' agreement with the system's recommendations was evaluated statistically. -The average satisfaction rate of the examiners was 95.6%, and for 83 out of the 85 cases, 97.6%.</p>	<p>-The majority of the examiners were satisfied with the recommendations of the system. -The inference system developed was confirmed as being reliable and effective for clinical use in orthodontics.</p>
Choi 2019 [13]	<p>316 cases: -160 surgical cases -156 non-surgical *204 learning set: -136 training set -68 validation set *112 test set</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Orthognathic surgery planning</p>	<p>-Lateral cephalograms</p>	<p>ANNs</p>	<p>1 orthodontist <u>Experience:</u> 10 years</p>	<p>-Success rate of surgery/non-surgery diagnosis: 96% -Success rate of detailed diagnosis: 91%</p>	<p>(+) effective -The success rate of surgery /non-surgery diagnosis was 96% for the total. -Class II and III surgical type classification showed 100% success rate in all sets.</p>	<p>This study suggests the artificial intelligent model using neural network machine learning could be applied for the diagnosis of orthognathic surgery cases.</p>

	<p><u>Mean age (M)</u> 22.1±4.8 years</p> <p><u>Mean age (F)</u> 23.6±6.5 years</p> <p><u>Males:</u> 123</p> <p><u>Females:</u> 193</p>					<p>-ICC value: [0.97;0.99]</p>	<p>-In each surgical case, the success rate of extraction diagnosis for Class II surgery was 97%. While for Class III surgery it was 88%. -the final diagnosis success rate was 91%.</p>	
Jung 2016 [40]	<p><u>156 cases</u></p> <p>*96 learning set: -64 training set -32 validation set *60 test set</p> <p><u>Mean age (M)</u> 23 years</p> <p><u>Mean age (F)</u> 25 years</p> <p><u>Males:</u> 62</p> <p><u>Females:</u> 94</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Extraction planning</p>	<p>-Lateral cephalograms</p>	<p>ANNs</p>	<p>1 orthodontist</p> <p><u>Experience:</u> 10 years</p>	<p>-Success rates of extraction/ non-extraction diagnosis: 93%</p> <p>-Success rate of detailed diagnosis of the extraction patterns: 84%</p> <p>-ICC value: [0.97;0.99]</p>	<p>(+) effective</p> <p>-In the diagnosis of extraction vs nonextraction, the decision-making success rate was 93%.</p> <p>-In the diagnosis of identical vs differential extraction, the success rate was 89%.</p> <p>-The final success rates were 85% in the learning set, 82% in the test set, and 84% in total.</p>	<p>AI expert systems with neural network machine learning could be useful in orthodontics. Improved performance was achieved by proper selection of the input data, appropriate organization of the modeling, and preferable generalization.</p>
Kim 2021 [46]	<p><u>960 cases</u></p> <p>*640 no surgery *320 surgery</p> <p>-<u>training set:</u> 810 -<u>test set:</u> 150</p> <p><u>Males:</u> 468 <u>Females:</u> 492</p> <p><u>Mean age:</u> 24.6 years SD: 4.9</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [15;37] years</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Orthognathic surgery planning</p>	<p>-Cephalograms</p>	<p>CNNs: ResNet-18, 34, 50, and 101</p>	<p>1 orthodontist</p> <p><u>Experience:</u> NM</p>	<p>Best performance was achieved by ResNet-18 :</p> <p>-<u>AUC:</u> 0.979 -<u>Accuracy:</u> 0.938 -<u>Sensitivity:</u> 0.882 -<u>Specificity:</u> 0.966</p>	<p>(+) effective</p> <p>The average success rate in the test set for the ResNet-18, 34, 50, and 101 was 93.80%, 93.60%, 91.13%, and 91.33%, respectively. In screening, ResNet-18 had the best performance with an area under the curve of 0.979, followed by ResNets-34, 50, and 101 at 0.974, 0.945, and 0.944, respectively.</p>	<p>The ResNet-18 and 34 models attained 93.80% and 93.60% success rates, respectively, in the test set; this confirmed the performance superiority compared with that of ResNet-50 and 101 models, which showed rates of 91.13% and 91.33%, respectively.</p>
Khanagar 2020 [43]	<p><u>16 research articles</u> [2009-2019]</p>	<p>-Diagnosis -Treatment planning -Predicting prognosis</p>	<p>-Patients clinical images -Radiographs -Cephalograms involving oral and maxillofacial structures</p>	<p>AI based models</p>	<p>-Expert opinions -Reference standards</p>	<p>Measurable or predictive outcomes such as: -Accuracy -Sensitivity -Specificity -ROC -AUC -ICC</p>	<p>(+) effective</p> <p>AI technology has been widely applied for determining need for orthodontic treatment needs and extractions, identifying cephalometric landmarks, determining the degree of maturation of the cervical vertebra, and predicting the facial attractiveness. Most used AI models were ANNs or CNNs.</p>	<p>The results from reported studies suggest that AI have performed exceptionally well, with an accuracy and precision similar to the trained examiners. These systems can be of great value in orthodontics.</p>

<p>Li 2019 [48]</p>	<p>302 cases: -222 extraction -80 non-extraction -182 training set -60 validation set -60 test set</p> <p><u>Mean age:</u> 17.16±5.71 years <u>Age range:</u> [9;40] years</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Extraction planning</p>	<p>Medical records before orthodontic treatment were collected: -demographic information -extraoral photos -intraoral photos -pre-treatment dental casts -lateral cephalometric measurements</p>	<p>ANNs</p>	<p>2 orthodontists</p> <p><u>Experience:</u> -26 years -12 years</p>	<p>-Accuracy: -Extraction/no extraction: 94% -Extraction patterns: 84.2% -Anchorage patterns: 92.8% -Sensitivity: 94.6% -Specificity: 93.8% -AUC: 0.982 (95% CI 0.968–0.995)</p>	<p>(+) effective -Considering the subjectivity of decision-making on extraction patterns, the model offers several practicable alternatives for doctors to choose, which makes it more applicable. -The most important features for prediction of the ANN are “crowding, upper arch” “ANB” and “curve of Spee”. -For handling continuous features with missing data, k-NN performs better.</p>	<p>These results indicate that the proposed method based on artificial neural networks can provide good guidance for orthodontic treatment planning for less-experienced orthodontists.</p>
<p>Lin 2020 [50]</p>	<p>56 cases: -10 surgical -46 non-surgical <u>Males:</u> 31 <u>Females:</u> 25 <u>Mean age:</u> <u>(T0):</u> 6.3 years <u>(T1):</u> 16.7 years</p>	<p>-Orthognathic surgery planning -Unilateral cleft lip and palate (UCLP)</p>	<p>-Lateral cephalograms At T0 and T1 <u>(T0):</u> before orthodontic / orthopedic treatment <u>(T1):</u> at least 15 years of age</p>	<p>Machine learning (ML): -Boruta method -XGBoost classifier</p>	<p>-1 orthodontist -1 surgeon</p>	<p>-10-fold cross validation Accuracy: 87.4% -Sensitivity: 97.83% -Specificity: 90.00% -F1-score: 0.714</p>	<p>(+) effective At the T0 stage, the ANB, PP-FH, CF, and facial convexity angle were selected as predictive parameters of the future need for orthognathic surgery, and had a 10-fold cross-validation accuracy of 87.4% with an F1-score of 0.714.</p>	<p>At age of 6 years it was possible to predict the future need for surgery to correct their sagittal skeletal discrepancy in patients with UCLP using cephalometric predictors with a good accuracy.</p>
<p>Nieri 2010 [62]</p>	<p>168 patients : -125 unilateral impaction -43 bilateral impaction <u>Males:</u> 40 <u>Females:</u> 128 <u>Mean age:</u> 17.2±6 years <u>Age range:</u> [12.8;52.0] years <u>Follow-up:</u> 17 years</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Impacted maxillary canines</p>	<p>Demographic, orthodontic, and periodontal variables</p>	<p>BNs</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>(+) effective All 168 impacted canines were successfully moved and aligned in the dental arches with healthy periodontiums. According to the Bayesian network analysis, bilateral impaction was associated with palatal impaction and longer treatment; the pre-treatment α-angle was a determinant for the duration of orthodontic traction, also because of the associations between greater angulation of impacted canines with more severe tooth displacement and with greater distance of the impacted canine from the occlusal plane.</p>	<p>-Bayesian network analysis was useful to identify possible relationships among the variables considered for diagnosis and treatment of impacted canines. -The post-treatment periodontal outcome was not related to the pre-treatment radiographic variables.</p>

Shin 2021 [75]	<p>840 cases *622 no surgery *218 surgery</p> <p><u>-Training set:</u> 273 surgery 98 no surgery</p> <p><u>-Validation set:</u> 30 surgery 11 no surgery</p> <p><u>-Test set:</u> 304 surgery 109 no surgery</p> <p><u>Males:</u> 461 <u>Females:</u> 379</p> <p><u>Mean age:</u> 23.2 years <u>Age range:</u> [19;29] years SD: 3.15</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Orthognathic surgery planning</p>	<p>-Transverse and longitudinal cephalograms</p>	<p>CNNs</p>	<p><u>6 specialists:</u> -2 orthodontists -3 maxillofacial surgeons -1 maxillofacial radiologist</p> <p><u>Experience:</u> NM</p>	<p><u>-Accuracy:</u> 0.954 <u>-Sensitivity:</u> 0.844 <u>-Specificity:</u> 0.993 <u>-a 2x2 contingency table</u></p>	<p>(+) effective Subsequently, 394 out of a total of 413 test data were properly classified. The accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were 0.954, 0.844, and 0.993, respectively.</p>	<p>It was found that a convolutional neural network can determine the need for orthognathic surgery with relative accuracy when using cephalogram.</p>
Suhail 2020 [77]	<p>287 pre-treatment patient records</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Extraction planning</p>	<p><u>Medical charts and conventional diagnostic records:</u> -lateral head films (cephalometric X-rays) -panoramic radiographs -facial photographs -intraoral photographs</p>	<p>Machine learning (ML): -neural network model -random forest ensemble classifier</p>	<p>5 orthodontists <u>Experience:</u> Average: 9 years</p>	<p><u>The out-of-bag accuracy</u> (an estimate of the test accuracy) plotted against the number of trees for the random forest model predicting the specific type of interaction ranged between 60% and 75%.</p>	<p>(+) effective -The agreement on the primary outcome of treatment between the different experts varied from 65% to 71% and agreement on either the primary or alternative outcome varied from 93% to 98% -the random forest classifier outperforms the neural network model for the prediction of the specific extraction treatment. Logistic regression can achieve marginally better performance only for the case of binary prediction when considering both the primary and alternative diagnoses from the expert.</p>	<p>A random forest ensemble classifier that simulates orthodontic tooth extraction/non-extraction decision-making was developed and confirmed to show a high performance, within the range of the inter-expert agreement.</p>

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Thanathornwong 2018 [82]</p>	<p>1) 1000 data-sets <u>Mean age:</u> 23.2 years <u>Age range:</u> [19;29] years SD: 3.15 <u>Males: 375</u> <u>Females: 625</u> <u>Mean age:</u> 17.4±2.51 years</p> <p>2) 20 new patients -evaluation set</p> <p><u>Males: 5</u> <u>Females: 15</u> <u>Age range:</u> [14;19] years</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Treatment needs</p>	<p>-Upper and lower arch impressions -Photographs</p>	<p>BNS</p>	<p>2 orthodontists</p> <p><u>Experience:</u> At least 5 years</p> <p>Assessed orthodontic treatment needs for the 20 new patients</p>	<p>-Accuracy: 0.96 -Sensitivity: 0.95 -Specificity: 1.00 -AUC: 0.91</p>	<p>(+) effective</p> <p>There was a high degree of agreement between the two orthodontists (kappa value = 0.894) in their diagnoses and their judgements regarding the need for orthodontic treatment. Also, there was a high degree of agreement between the decision support system and orthodontists, A (kappa value = 1.00) and B (kappa value = 0.894).</p>	<p>The system delivered promising results; it showed a high degree of accuracy in classifying patients into groups needing and not needing orthodontic treatment.</p>
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Xie 2010 [91]</p>	<p><u>200 cases:</u> -120 extraction -80 non-extraction</p> <p>-180 training set -20 testing set</p> <p><u>Age range:</u> [11;15] years</p>	<p>-Tooth malocclusion -Extraction planning</p>	<p>-Cast measurements -Lateral cephalograms</p>	<p>ANNs</p>	<p>NM</p>	<p>-Accuracy: 80%</p>	<p>(+) effective</p> <p>When data from the 180 patients that had been trained were tested, the result was 100%, as expected. The untrained data from 20 patients in the testing set were 80% correct (ie, 16 cases were forecasted successfully). In the meantime, the relative contributions of the 23 input indices to the final output index (extraction/non-extraction) were calculated. “Anterior teeth uncovered by incompetent lips” and “IMPA (L1-MP)” were the two indices that gave the biggest contributions. Sequentially; the index of FMA (FH-MP) gave the smallest contribution.</p>	<p>-The constructed artificial neural network in this study was effective, with 80% accuracy, in determining whether extraction or non-extraction treatment was best for malocclusion patients between 11 and 15 years old. -When the clinician is predicting whether an orthodontic treatment requires extraction, the indices: “anterior teeth uncovered by incompetent lips” and “IMPA (L1-MP)” should be taken into consideration first.</p>

6. Data sum-up

The final number of included articles in this review was 28 distributed among the investigated 3 sub-interventions.

6.1. Artificial intelligence

The number of included trials in this section was 12; 10 of which were DTA studies and the other 2 being a retrospective cohort and a recent systematic review. The sample size in all the trials ranged from 56 (Lin 2020) to 1000 data sets (Thanathornwong 2018) with a total of 4370 patient records.

Age range across individual studies was from 6.3 to 52 years of age, and a mean age of 19.48 years. It is safe to assume that most of the participants involved in this intervention are primarily teenagers followed by young adults.

Diversified AI approaches were used: Fuzzy modelling, ANNs, BNs, CNNs and ML (Boruta method, XGBoost classifier, neural network model, random forest classifier). ANNs was the most used model (4 studies [13,40,48,91]) followed by BNs [62,82] and CNNs [46,75] (2 studies each).

The focus of all interventions was orthodontic treatment planning and decision making with slightly varying study factors. The matters of investigation were:

Tooth malocclusion, extraction planning, orthognathic surgery planning, treatment needs, impacted maxillary canines, unilateral cleft lip and palate, selecting headgear pull type, diagnosis and predicting prognosis.

Different modalities were used: dental casts, intra and extra-oral photographs, panoramic radiographs, lateral cephalograms and demographic information.

All comparisons were reference standards executed by experienced clinicians apart from 2 studies (Xie 2010: DTA) (Nieri 2010: cohort) that did not mention any comparison details. The number of experienced specialists ranged from 1 to 8, that had on average 12.39 years of experience.

The evaluation of AI models' performance was reported through: examiners' agreement and average satisfaction, success rates of the AI model, ICC value,

accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, AUC, F1-score, and 10-fold cross validation accuracy. All AI models were judged as effective.

6.2. Nanotechnology

The number of included trials this section was 8; 6 RCTs and 2 CCTs. The sample size in all the trials ranged from 12 (Venkatesan 2020) to 66 subjects (Farhadian 2016) with a total of 291 patients, it should be noted that 3 studies (2 RCTs and 1 CCT) had a split mouth design. Five trials have mentioned sample size calculation, whereas it was not specified in the remaining trials.

Age range across individual studies was from 7 to 37 years of age, with 5 studies having participants with a calculated mean age of 16.46 years. There was a predominance of teenagers involved in this intervention. There were no significant gender imbalances, just in one study (Jahanbin 2017) that had 25 females and no males, while 2 other studies (Venkatesan 2020) (Alam 2021) did not mention patients' gender. Follow-up periods varied from 1 month to 6 months which was acceptable depending on the study objective.

In each study, Different interventions investigating the use of nano-particles were analysed; Nano-Hydroxyapatite toothpaste [7], Silver nanoparticles removable retainers [26,29], Nanosilver mouthwash [4], Nano amorphous calcium phosphate composite [36], TiO₂ nanoparticle coated NiTi archwires [85], Casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate nanocomplexes Mousse [87], and Nano-bio fusion gingival gel [3].

All comparisons were made to conventional standard treatment without use of nanotechnology.

Reported outcomes and outcome measures varied from one study to another, however most of them focused on the anti-bacterial properties of some nanoparticles (silver, titanium dioxide) and the effects of incorporating active nano-complexes on common orthodontic problems like white spot lesions.

These outcomes were:

- White spot lesion extent and degree of enamel remineralization (fluorescence / photography/ plaque index /EDI) [4,7,36,85,87]

- Number of *S. mutans*, Planktonic growth and biofilm formation of cariogenic bacteria (CFU) [26,29,36,85]
- Surface roughness and surface topography [85]
- Periodontal assessment of treatment-induced gingivitis [3]

All the trials were comparative studies, in which direct inter-group comparisons were made and *P* values were used for statistical significance.

6.3. Regenerative therapy (Stem cells / PRF)

The number of included trials in this section was 8; 4 RCTs, 1 CCT, 2 cohorts and 1 recent systematic review (Francisco 2020).

The sample size in all the trials ranged from 8 (Tehranchi 2018) to 30 subjects (Gonen 2019) with a total of 130 patients, it should be noted that 4 studies had a split mouth design (3 RCTs and 1 CCT). Only 3 trials have mentioned sample size calculation.

Age range across individual studies was from 4 months to 51 years of age, with a calculated mean age of 21.76 years for PRF articles and 5.11 months for stem cells study. Participants were generally young adults and teenagers in PRF studies and infants in SC studies. Overall, there were no significant gender imbalances. Follow-up ranged from 4 months to 2 years for PRF and 10 years for stem cells which was acceptable regarding the study objective.

The research identified 7 articles focused on PRF but only one study about stem cells [56]. This latter, investigated the effect of SC injection in surgical wound in cleft lip and palate patients while PRF studies looked into: associating PRF with periodontal surgery (1 study [15]), speeding-up orthodontic treatment with PRF (5 studies), alveolar cleft reconstruction and tooth movement (1 study: SR [27])

All comparisons were made to conventional standard treatment without use of any regenerative therapy, apart from one observational non-comparative cohort study (Muñoz 2016).

Reported outcomes and outcome measures varied from one study to another, however most of them focused on the regenerative effects of PRF and SC and their effects on accelerating orthodontic treatment and improving its outcomes.

These outcomes were:

- Gingival thickness, gingival biotype modification, width of keratinized gingiva, vestibular bone thickness, Bone regeneration [15,31]
- hard tissue reconstruction of alveolar bone [27,31,61]
- Rate of orthodontic tooth movement, duration of orthodontic treatment, rate of distalization and inclination of maxillary canines [27,31,61,70,81]
- Pain / post-surgical inflammation and infection [60]
- Short-term orthodontic stability [60]
- Lip soft tissue inflammatory process in first 48h, Lip transitory hypertrophic scar, Palatal dehiscence, Palatal fistula, and Fibrosis between soft and hard palate at the second surgical time (SC study) [56]

All the comparative studies had direct inter-group comparisons and *P* values were used for statistical significance.

6.4. Quantitative synthesis of the results

Depending on the main outcomes across the 3 sub-interventions, the aim was to conduct a meta-analysis on one of those interventions that had the most clinical significance and evidence concerning orthodontic practice. From a sample size and number of studies' perspective, artificial intelligence seems to be the most suitable candidate for a meta-analysis.

On the other side, the heterogenous interventions and treatments performed in the nanotechnology and regenerative therapy's included studies do not allow a quantitative synthesis of the results. Moreover, the heterogeneity in the methodologies and design rule out a meta-analysis for these 2 sub-interventions.

A meta-analysis of effectiveness could not be performed for artificial intelligence, due to the fact that the AI models' performance was not evaluated in a clinical intervention to assess effectiveness.

Thus, a meta-analysis of diagnostic test accuracy studies for artificial intelligence was conducted. While, a qualitative synthesis of the results was performed for nanotechnology and regenerative therapy.

Meta-analysis

1. Objective

Meta-analysis refers to the critical evaluation, statistical combination, and analysis of data from comparable independent primary studies focused on the same question, which aims to generate a quantitative estimate of the studied phenomenon [57].

Thus, the executed meta-analysis had the objective of evaluating the performance and effectiveness of AI models for orthodontic treatment planning and decision-making.

2. Methods

The paired nature of the main outcome measures (sensitivity/specificity) makes meta-analysis of data from studies of diagnostic test accuracy more complicated than most other types of meta-analysis [12].

Previously, in the qualitative synthesis, diagnostic accuracy measures (sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, AUC) were reported when available. For the studies that documented sensitivities and specificities, if two by two contingency tables were not available, counts were back calculated based on reported accuracy measures to build forest plots. A meta-analysis was undertaken but limited to only 5 studies, and that is because in most studies the raw data necessary to meta-analyse diagnostic accuracy measures were unavailable. These 5 AI studies reported enough data that allowed to generate two by two contingency tables for each of them. These studies had similar research hypotheses and were combined by the reviewers in a meta-analysis [46,48,50,75,82]

Sensitivity (Se), specificity (Sp), likelihood ratio (LR) and diagnostic odds ratio (DOR) are the included metrics for the analysis (Appendix 6) [97]. First, the random-effects model was employed for descriptive statistical combination of studies and then a Hierarchical method: the bivariate model was used for pooling and quantitative combination of studies. Subsequently, a summary receiver operating characteristics (SROC) curve was plotted and publication bias was evaluated using the Deeks' funnel plot asymmetry test.

Statistical analysis and graphical representations were done with the help of “OpenMeta[Analyst]” [86], “MetaDTA” [28,68] and “Stata/MP 16 (StataCorp)” [76] with the use of the MIDAS package [21].

2.1. Sensitivity and specificity

In medical diagnosis, test sensitivity refers to a test's ability to correctly identify those who have the target condition (true positive rate), whereas test specificity refers to the test's ability to correctly identify those who do not have the target condition (true negative rate) [95] (Appendix 6).

2.2. SROC plot

A receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC curve) is a graph that shows how well a classification model performs across all classification thresholds. This curve plots two parameters: True Positive Rate (sensitivity) and False Positive Rate (1-specificity) [114].

The SROC plot has been recommended to represent the performance of diagnostic tests, based on data from a meta-analysis. It displays a summary of tests performances, a visual representation of the threshold effect, and data heterogeneity in the ROC space between sensitivity and specificity; in the SROC plot, each circle represents a single study, summary operating sensitivity specificity, and SROC curve with both confidence and prediction regions. The dashed line around the pooled point estimate represents the 95 percent confidence region (Appendix 6).

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Statistics and Plots

The first step in data synthesis is to calculate descriptive statistics for each primary study. These statistics include sensitivity (Se), specificity (Sp), positive likelihood ratio (PLR), negative likelihood ratio (NLR), and the diagnostic odds ratio (DOR) from the diagnostic 2-by-2 tables of individual studies [45].

Separate pooling of DTA metrics of the 5 reviewed studies was executed with the use of the Random-effects (DerSimonian and Laird) method for meta-analysis with 95% confidence interval and a correction factor of 0.5. This method is a variation on the inverse-variance method to incorporate an assumption that the different studies are estimating different, yet related, intervention effects [102].

(Figure 8) shows the inputs for each study (TP/FN/FP/TN) in the interface of OpenMeta[Analyst]. (Figure 9) shows the Diagnostic random effects model summary generated from OpenMeta[Analyst].

study name	year	TP	FN	FP	TN	sens.	lower	upper	spec.	lower	upper
Kim	2021	44	6	3	97	0.880	0.758	0.945	0.970	0.911	0.990
Li	2019	210	12	5	75	0.946	0.907	0.969	0.937	0.858	0.974
Lin	2020	45	1	1	9	0.978	0.861	0.997	0.900	0.533	0.986
Shin	2021	302	2	17	92	0.993	0.974	0.998	0.844	0.763	0.901
Thanathornwong	2018	760	40	0	200	0.949	0.932	0.963	0.998	0.962	1.000

Figure 8: Study-level outcomes

Negative Likelihood Ratio summary								
Diagnostic Random-Effects Model (k = 5)								
Negative Likelihood Ratio - Model Results				Negative Likelihood Ratio - Heterogeneity				
Estimate	Lower bound	Upper bound	p-Value	τ^2 (Tau2)	Q(df=4)	Het. p-Value	I^2	
0.035	0.009	0.136	< 0.001	1.875	32.846	< 0.001	87.822	
Positive likelihood ratio summary								
Diagnostic Random-Effects Model (k = 5)								
Positive Likelihood Ratio - Model Results				Positive Likelihood Ratio - Heterogeneity				
Estimate	Lower bound	Upper bound	p-Value	τ^2 (Tau2)	Q(df=4)	Het. p-Value	I^2	
16.709	6.517	42.836	< 0.001	0.722	15.107	0.004	73.522	
Sensitivity summary								
Diagnostic Random-Effects Model (k = 5)								
Sensitivity - Model Results				Sensitivity - Heterogeneity				
Estimate	Lower bound	Upper bound	p-Value	τ^2 (Tau2)	Q(df=4)	Het. p-Value	I^2	
0.955	0.917	0.976	< 0.001	0.339	14.095	0.007	71.622	
Specificity summary								
Diagnostic Random-Effects Model (k = 5)								
Specificity - Model Results				Specificity - Heterogeneity				
Estimate	Lower bound	Upper bound	p-Value	τ^2 (Tau2)	Q(df=4)	Het. p-Value	I^2	
0.945	0.855	0.98	< 0.001	0.976	16.863	0.002	76.279	
odds ratio summary								
Diagnostic Random-Effects Model (k = 5)								
Odds ratio - Model Results				Odds ratio - Heterogeneity				
Estimate	Lower bound	Upper bound	p-Value	τ^2 (Tau2)	Q(df=4)	Het. p-Value	I^2	
479.02	187.212	1225.674	< 0.001	0.395	6.221	0.183	35.705	

Figure 9: Diagnostic random effects model summary

(Figures 10,11,12) show the sensitivity, specificity, PLR, NLR and DOR forest plots. While (Figure 13) shows the SROC plot, the plot is rendered so that the size of the data points reflects the sample size of each study.

Figure 10: Sensitivity and specificity forest plots according to the random effects model

Figure 11: PLR and NLR forest plots according to the random effects model

A PLR that is greater than 5 and an NLR that is less than 0.2 provide "strong" diagnostic evidence. All the studies exhibited a PLR>5 but with varying values, as (Thanathornwong 2018) had by far the highest estimate value PLR=381.67. While for the other studies the values ranged from 6.37 (Shin 2021) to 29.33 (Kim 2021). As for NLR, all studies had a value less than 0.2. (Shin 2021) had the lowest NLR=0.008 whereas (Kim 2021) had the highest value NLR=0.124.

Figure 12: DOR forest plots according to the random effects model

Figure 13: ROC plot

In the ROC plot, variations in study estimates are noticeable. In fact, (Thanathornwong 2018) study appears to have the most study weight and (Lin 2020) having the least.

3.2. Assessment of heterogeneity

The variability between studies is referred to as heterogeneity. Heterogeneity can be caused by chance, errors in analytical methodology, and/or differences in study design, protocol, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and diagnostic thresholds. Using Cochran Q or Higgins' I² statistics to assess heterogeneity is an option, but they may not be sufficient on their own because they do not account for threshold effect.

For that reason, visual evaluation of coupled forest plot and SROC plot along with Spearman correlation analysis to find threshold effect is recommended [47].

To investigate Homogeneity of the included studies, Chi-square test (Cochrane Q statistic), the Higgins' I^2 , the τ^2 (Tau2) test, and P values were calculated and generated through *OpenMeta[Analyst]* (Figure 9).

A p value less than 0.10 on the Q test or an I^2 statistic greater than 50% are considered to indicate substantial heterogeneity among DTA study results [88].

There was a noticeable heterogeneity in NLR, PLR, Sp and Se (I^2 : 87.82, 73.52, 71.62, and 76.28 respectively). While the odds ratio showed low heterogeneity (I^2 : 35.70, $p>0.1$).

It is always advisable to investigate potential causes of heterogeneity, although there are too few studies available to do so adequately. Consequently, the meta-regression and subgroup analyses, which ideally should have been conducted to explore heterogeneity, were not carried out due to the small number of studies and the lack of sufficient data [45].

Plotting data on paired forest plots and SROC, on the other hand, can provide a useful, albeit subjective, insight into the presence or absence of heterogeneity. When viewing the ROC plot, heterogeneity is indicated by how closely the included data fits to an SROC curve, rather than how close the points are to each other in ROC space. Data that fits a typical shoulder-shaped SROC curve tightly indicates low heterogeneity [94]. The ROC plot, shows that this criterion is not satisfied, as the study of (Thanathornwong 2018) seems to be astray from the curve made by other studies (Figure 13). Thus, heterogeneity is present across these studies.

The threshold effect, which occurs when discrepancies in sensitivities and specificities or LRs emerge due to various cut-offs or thresholds used in different studies to define a positive (or negative) test result, is one of the primary reasons of heterogeneity in test accuracy studies [96].

Another method of investigation of heterogeneity is checking the coupled forest plot. A coupled forest plot of sensitivity and specificity (Figure 14) is a side-by-side display of two forest plots exhibiting sensitivity and specificity in which the order

of individual studies is sorted according to one of the parameters (e.g., in ascending order of the sensitivity values). If a threshold effect exists, the sensitivity and specificity will vary in an inverse manner. As a result, the overall disposition of the coupled forest plot will have a V or an inverted-V shape [47].

Figure 14: Coupled Sp and Se forest plots with ascending order of the sensitivity values

The arrangement of this coupled forest plots exhibits this V shape, even though some oddity in this V shape can be noted, which seems to be primarily due to the study of (Thanathornwong 2018) (Figure 14). The cause of heterogeneity was further investigated by performing a sensitivity analysis through MetaDTA where the study (Thanathornwong 2018) was eliminated, which was highly suspected as a potential cause for heterogeneity. Then, the following coupled forest plots were obtained (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Coupled Sp and Se forest plots without the study of Thanathornwong and with ascending order of the sensitivity values

It is noticeable that the V shape is more regular. Therefore, the presence of two different heterogeneity causes is most likely; the first one being the threshold effect outlined by the presence of the V shape and the second one being the heterogeneity caused by the study of (Thanathornwong 2018) which needs to be further investigated.

There is a variety of reasons for inherent heterogeneity in DTA research, beyond that which may be explained by chance due to small sample sizes. Differences in study patient populations, methods of administering tests and interpreting results, the type of reference standard used, and positivity thresholds are examples that contribute to heterogeneity [49]. Furthermore, many DTA studies are retrospective observational studies with a low level of evidence and a potentially high risk of bias [47].

3.4. Quantitative (Meta-Analysis) Data Synthesis

A hierarchical method: bivariate model (maximum likelihood) was applied for pooling sensitivities and specificities across studies using OpenMeta[Analyst]. It estimates the summary parameters: sensitivity and specificity across primary studies. It is presented as the preferred method in the Cochrane Handbook [47].

Parameter	Estimate	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
Sensitivity	0.965	0.921	0.985
Specificity	0.962	0.878	0.989
False Positive Rate	0.038	0.011	0.122
Random Effects Correlation	-0.675		
Diagnostic Odds Ratio	695.537	232.742	2078.572
Likelihood Ratio +ve	25.304	7.686	83.310
Likelihood Ratio -ve	0.036	0.016	0.081
logit(sensitivity)	3.317	2.463	4.171
logit(specificity)	3.228	1.973	4.482

Figure 16: Bivariate summary

The sensitivity, specificity, False positive rate (FPR), DOR, and area under the curve (AUC) with 95% CI of AI models' performance were: 0.965 (95% CI 0.921-0.985), 0.962 (95% CI 0.878-0.989), 0.038 (95% CI 0.011-0.122), 695.537 (95% CI 232.742-2078.572), 0.99 (95% CI 0.98 - 1.00), respectively. And a random effects

correlation of -0.675 (Figure 16). A strong negative correlation between specificity and sensitivity is indicative of a threshold effect and suggests that the pairs of parameters represent the same DOR [49].

Pooled analysis of the crude value of TP, FP, FN, and TN revealed that the accuracy of the AI algorithms reached 95.47%.

A clinically useful test shows a PLR > 5.0 and a NLR < 0.2. Which was the case for the included pooled studies.

For visual assessment of threshold effect, the higher the cut-off value, the greater the specificity and the lower the sensitivity [45]. This sensitivity-specificity dependency based on threshold variability can be assessed a priori using a rank correlation test such as Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. In MIDAS (Stata) [21], the proportion of variation due to threshold effects is calculated as the squared correlation coefficient estimated from the between-study covariance parameter and it had a value of 0.44. The threshold effect is regarded as substantial if a significant correlation exists, with a correlation coefficient of 0.67 or higher. The determined value was comprised between 0.36 - 0.67 and thus, indicating a moderate threshold effect.

A statistically significant level of heterogeneity existed among the studies' data, and it showed that it was related moderately to the threshold effect and possibly the (Thanathornwong 2018) study.

Figure 17: Bivariate model SROC curve

The magnitude of heterogeneity is represented by showing the prediction region in SROC space, centred on the average operating point. The prediction region represents variance from between-study heterogeneity, whereas the confidence region depicts uncertainty in the overall average value produced by sampling variability. Review authors will notice that where heterogeneity is high, the 95% prediction region is much bigger than the 95% confidence region. Prediction regions also take account of correlations in variation in sensitivity and specificity, and variation in positivity threshold [47,73]. This was the case for the present SROC space; the 95% prediction region is much larger than the 95% confidence region and the SROC curve does not seem to include all studies (Figure 17).

Figure 18: Bivariate model SROC curve after excluding Thanathornwong 2018

A sensitivity analysis on the SROC curve was conducted to further assess the implication of (Thanathornwong 2018) in overall heterogeneity. As can be seen in the Bivariate model SROC curve (Figure 18) after excluding (Thanathornwong 2018), the 95% prediction region and the 95% confidence region are tightly fit compared to the original model and the included data from other studies fit closely in the SROC curve. It is now clear that (Thanathornwong 2018) is a source of

heterogeneity due to its design, sample size, different AI algorithm, or the application of the correction factor 0.5 due to its specificity=1).

Parameter	Estimate	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
Sensitivity	0.967	0.902	0.990
Specificity	0.925	0.850	0.964
False Positive Rate	0.075	0.036	0.150
Random Effects Correlation	-1.000		
Diagnostic Odds Ratio	367.108	161.570	834.115
Likelihood Ratio +ve	12.958	6.460	25.989
Likelihood Ratio -ve	0.035	0.012	0.105
logit(sensitivity)	3.388	2.222	4.555
logit(specificity)	2.517	1.736	3.298

Figure 19: Bivariate summary after excluding Thanathornwong 2018

Ideally, (Thanathornwong 2018) would be excluded from the meta-analysis and a meta-regression along with sub-group analysis would be performed, but this could not be carried since the pool of included studies is relatively too small.

After pooling the DTA parameters without the study of (Thanathornwong 2018), Sensitivity was 0.967 (95% CI 0.902-0.990), Specificity was 0.925 (95% CI 0.850-0.964), FPR 0.075 (95% CI 0.036-0.15), DOR 367.108 (95% CI 161.570-834.115), and a random effects correlation of -1 (Figure 19).

Excluding (Thanathornwong 2018) did not have much impact on pooled sensitivity and specificity but it increased the FPR and decreased the DOR (the discriminative power of a diagnostic test) which decreased the overall estimate accuracy of AI models.

The higher the value of the DOR (i.e., a single indicator of test performance) ranging from zero to infinity, the higher the value of the AUC, which ranges from zero to one. The higher amount of DOR is indicative of the fact that the approaches can determine the right treatment plan with high overall accuracy [30].

On the other hand, the random effects correlation indicated a perfectly negative correlation (-1), which can mean that there are not enough data to estimate all the parameters reliably. It should be noted that sensitivity analysis did not show any

substantial difference in the results when excluding the other studies, apart from (Thanathornwong 2018).

3.5. Assessment of publication bias

Publication bias is a bias that is widely assumed to exist because statistically insignificant results tend to not be disclosed, resulting in a potentially exaggerated pooled estimate in a systematic review. In a meta-analysis of DTA studies, DOR as a single indication of diagnostic accuracy is favoured above the paired sensitivity and specificity to examine possible publication bias. In Deeks funnel plot method, x-axis is natural logarithm of DOR and y-axis is $1/\sqrt{\text{ESS}}$ effective sample size (ESS) According to Deeks et al. [17], this is the preferred method for meta-analysis of diagnostic test accuracy studies owing to its high statistical power.

The Deeks' funnel plot [84] of studies exhibited a grossly symmetrical shape with respect to the regression line (Figure 20), and the asymmetry test showed no apparent evidence of publication bias ($p=0.20$). This assessment is of low degree of certainty since there were only 5 studies to assess.

Figure 20: Deeks funnel plot for publication bias assessment

3.6. Summary of findings

The GRADE summary of findings table was done through GRADEpro GDT [110,115]. For assessing the certainty of the body of evidence across outcomes, the study design was set as case-control type accuracy study, the risk of bias and inconsistency as serious, indirectness and imprecision as not serious, publication bias as undetected and effect was determined as large.

The values of pooled sensitivity and specificity of the 5 studies indicated that the overall rates of correct predictions of orthodontic treatment plans were high. Either in predicting orthodontic treatment needs, extractions needs or orthognathic surgery needs, the AI models exhibited high predictive values and a correct classification of patients needing those interventions and patients not needing those interventions with small error margins.

However, these findings are still insufficient to draw definite conclusions, and various limitations must be addressed.

Table 8: GRADE summary of findings

What is the effectiveness and performance of AI models for orthodontic treatment planning and decision-making?

Patient or population: Orthodontic patients' records

Settings: Orthodontic clinic / departments

New test: AI models treatment planning and decision-making systems

Reference test: Reference standards (by experienced clinicians)

Pooled sensitivity: 0.96 (95% CI: 0.92 to 0.98) | **Pooled specificity:** 0.96 (95% CI: 0.88 to 0.99)

Test result	Number of results per 1,000 patients tested (95% CI)			Number of participants (studies)	Certainty of the Evidence (GRADE)
	Prevalence 20% typically in orthognathic surgery needs	Prevalence 50% typically in orthodontic treatment needs	Prevalence 40% typically in extraction needs		
True positives	193 (184 to 197)	483 (461 to 493)	386 (368 to 394)	1921 (5)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate
False negatives	7 (3 to 16)	17 (7 to 39)	14 (6 to 32)		
True negatives	770 (702 to 791)	481 (439 to 495)	577 (527 to 593)	1921 (5)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate
False positives	30 (9 to 98)	19 (5 to 61)	23 (7 to 73)		

CI: confidence interval

GRADE working group grades of certainty of the evidence

⊕⊕⊕⊕ **High:** Further research is very unlikely to change our confidence in the estimate of effect.

⊕⊕⊕○ **Moderate:** Further research is likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and may change the estimate.

⊕⊕○○ **Low:** Further research is very likely to have an important impact on our confidence in the estimate of effect and is likely to change the estimate.

⊕○○○ **Very low:** Any estimate of effect is very uncertain.

Retrospective studies with internal validation data used to develop the model, may substantially overestimate algorithm's performance. However, without external data evaluation, the algorithm may result in unanticipated adverse effects such as misdiagnosis in clinical settings. Huge datasets are required to ensure generalizability for populations with significant heterogeneity and researchers should employ external validation data sets and try for as low as reasonably achievable false negative rate and false positive rate.

Discussion

1. Discussion of the review methodology

A systematic review is a review of a clearly defined question that uses systematic and explicit procedures to find, select, and critically appraise relevant research, as well as gather and analyse data from the included studies. To analyse and summarize the findings of the included research, statistical methods (meta-analysis) may or may not be utilized. (Cochrane Collaboration, 2014). The following review adhered to the recommended standards and a PRISMA 2020 Checklist was filled (Appendix 7).

1.1. The research question

The review's question was formulated according to the PICOS framework as indicated for the systematic reviews of effectiveness.

1.2. The review team

For gathering a review team, it is recommended by the NASEM [22] to establish a team with the appropriate knowledge and experience on conducting a systematic review. The work team must comprise experts in the relevant clinical content areas, systematic review methodologies, searching for relevant evidence, and quantitative approaches.

To satisfy these standards, the review team was comprised of:

- A professor of orthodontics in the department of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopaedics at the University clinic of Dental Medicine of Monastir (ID), who is a well-renowned researcher with experience in conducting scientific studies and expertise in systematic reviews protocols.
- A thesis candidate in dental medicine and a former intern in the department of dentofacial orthopaedics at the University clinic of Dental Medicine of Monastir (JM) who has an extensive research background on the management of systematic reviews and meta-analyses.

1.3. The databases

According to the NASEM report and AMSTAR 2 guidelines, using a single database is not recommended and at least two databases have to be searched in the SR/MA, for the reason that a systematic review aims to provide a global image [22,80]. Thus, this review included 5 different databases and the search was carried out in each database conforming to its proper search strategy and vocabulary.

- The data banks MEDLINE via PubMed, is one of the most accessible, providing open access to all interested clinicians and researchers and the public in general [106].
- EBSCO host (Dentistry & Oral Sciences Source database) provides a range of library database services.
- ScienceDirect is one of the leading platforms of peer-reviewed literature that provides subscription-based access to a large database of scientific and medical research.
- Scopus is an abstract and citation indexing database with full-text links that is produced by the Elsevier Co.
- Web of Science (All databases: WOS, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO), is a subscription-based database of bibliographic citations of multidisciplinary areas. The conducted search in web of science database included 5 different incorporated databases: Web Of Science core collection, Korean Journal Database, MEDLINE, Russian Science Citation Index, and Scientific Electronic Library On-line. So, by extension, 8 different databases were searched [25].

1.4. Search strategy

The aim of the Search stage was to identify all accessible published and unpublished work that addressed the review question. The selected databases were thoroughly searched using controlled vocabulary combinations that were changed for each database, as operationalized by the search terms. Nonetheless,

the results remained vague, redundant, and irrelevant. This was primarily because there were multiple terms that were not distinct MeSH terms.

The primary strategy resulted in 1333 (AI: 663, NANO: 456, STEM CELLS/PRF: 214) studies after omitting the redundancies.

The search has been updated at intervals that correspond to the rate at which new information for the addressed research question is generated. A catch-up search was performed on the 19th of January 2022 in the PubMed database.

Restrictions were set on the date of publication, since the review interventions inherent to this scientific review are new areas of interest in the scientific community, starting to gain popularity in the last decade. Because of that, the search was extended over to 2 decades. In addition, only articles in English and French languages have been included.

Systematic reviews have been included in the pool of results because they represent the strongest type of evidence especially when having good methodological quality.

There were 2 systematic review included in this review (AI: Khanagar 2020, PRF: Francisco 2020), which were just recently published and had good methodological qualities. Therefore, their inclusion allowed the examination of included studies in those SRs which were out of scope for this current review. Furthermore, it allowed the review team to avoid duplications, and save time and resources by circumventing further extraction of articles analysed in these SRs but not found in the search results.

Even though the search strategy was well-grounded, the references of eligible studies still needed to be scrutinized to identify any missed articles.

Grey literature databases (Open Grey and WorldCat) were checked but no articles were retrieved.

The irrelevant or/and lacking results may be attributed to the Boolean operators or to the search filters, but can also be due to human error. As an example, for nanotechnology, some studies could have been missed since they did not use the word 'nano' in their articles.

Reference manager software, *EndNote™ 20* and *Rayyan*, were used to record the process and keep track of the decisions made for each paper.

1.5. Data collection and data extraction

Data extraction refers to the method through which researchers collect and transcribe data from individual studies [22]. Whether a quantitative or a qualitative synthesis is planned, the evaluation of intervention effectiveness should begin with a clear and systematic description of the included studies.

For the purposes of this systematic review, a customized data collection form has been elaborated for retrieving relevant data (Appendix 2), and to prevent data extraction errors, the process for each study was doubled and then the results were compared.

1.6. The findings

1.6.1. Summary of main results

The objective of this review was to evaluate the effectiveness of AI, nanotechnology and PRF/SC in orthodontic treatment planning and delivery compared to conventional treatments and reference standards, and thereby propose recommendations for clinicians and future research. The final number of included trials in this review is 28 with a total of 4791 (AI: 4370, NANO: 291, SC/PRF: 130) participants. Overall, 36% of studies were DTAs, 36% RCTs, 11% CCTs, 11% Cohorts and 7% SRs. For further details, please refer to the “Data sum-up” in the results section.

1.6.2. Overall completeness and applicability of evidence

A systematic review is a type of research in and of itself, and by definition, can cover much broader problems than single empirical studies can [10].

Indeed, systematic reviews with meta-analysis are at the top of the 'hierarchy of evidence,' since they have the greatest potential for providing the most important practical implications.

Figure 21: Hierarchy of scientific evidence

The inclusion and exclusion criteria that are immanent to this work are intended to ensure the inclusion of high-quality, relevant studies. In fact, the review team chose to only include human high evidence studies like recent systematic reviews and trials that had randomization and/or control groups and/or adequate follow-up periods, and to exclude animal/in-vitro studies, case reports, case series and expert opinions because they do not procure as high evidence as desired. Conference papers and books were excluded as well since they usually are not peer-reviewed. For AI, diagnostic test accuracy studies had to be included which are usually cross-sectional or case-control in nature, since AI is still an emerging field of study in orthodontics and researchers are still evaluating its efficacy and performance and comparing it to reference standards. Subsequently, at the time being, it is almost impossible to find DTA-RCT studies that implement an AI model into a trial and refer to its outcomes as guidelines for treatment and then evaluating its treatment effectiveness compared to a conventional treatment [90]. Furthermore, notes on the quality of each included study were made to support the overview of methodological shortcomings that bias the literature.

Although there is no consensus on the optimal strategy to assess study quality and bias risk, most methods encompass issues such as appropriateness of study design for addressing the research objectives; participant or condition selection methods; measurement of study variables; control of confounding; appropriate use of

statistics; quality of reporting; quality of intervention/condition; generalizability; author conflicts of interest. In this review, the JBI critical appraisal checklists were used [105], which yielded in the following results:

For AI: 2 DTA studies had high risk of bias, 5 DTA studies had moderate risk of bias, and 3 DTA studies had low risk of bias, while the SR and the cohort study had both low risk of bias.

For nanotechnology: all studies had low risk of bias apart from one RCT study that had moderate risk of bias.

Whereas for regenerative therapy: the SR had low risk of bias, the 2 cohort studies had moderate risk of bias, the CCT study had a low risk of bias, while for the 4 RCTs; 2 were moderate risk, 1 was high risk and 1 was low risk of bias.

Concerning articles evaluation; the “2011 OCEBM Levels of Evidence” [34] and “GRADE recommendations” were used to assess the quality, level of evidence, and strength of recommendations [115]. According to these protocols, 10 AI articles had an OCEBM level of 4 and a GRADE recommendation of 1-C, this is because these articles were DTA case-controls in nature and it was difficult to draw recommendations for practice from them. Only one DTA study had an OCEBM level of 2 because it had a cross-sectional design. On the other hand, the SR included had a high quality with an OCEBM level of 1 and a GRADE recommendation of 1-B. It should be noted that levels of evidence and strength of recommendations in early DTA studies are just indicative and should not be taken in a judgemental way since they are still in the developmental phase and not ready for clinical use.

For nanotechnology, 3 studies had a high quality and level of evidence with an OCEBM rating of 2 and a GRADE of 1-A, 2 studies were low quality (OCEBM:3, GRADE: 1-C) while the remaining ones were considered moderate quality.

For regenerative therapy, the SR included had an OCEBM level of 1 and a GRADE recommendation of 1-B which was considered high quality. 2 studies were low quality (OCEBM:3, GRADE: 1-C) and the remaining studies were considered moderate quality.

Thus, consistent conclusions could be drawn from this review. In fact, this systematic review has been able to meet its aim as the results regarding the impact of the studied interventions were satisfying and we were confronted with solid findings.

2. Discussion of the main data

2.1. Bias, limitations, and strength points

2.1.1. Bias

Bias in oral health research is a type of systematic flaw that can influence scientific findings and distort inference [11].

Figure 22: Major sources of bias in clinical research

It is almost impossible to eliminate bias since the process of attempting to do so may add new bias or render a study less generalizable. As a result, the goal is to minimize bias and to help investigators and readers understand its residual effects, limiting data misinterpretation and misuse.

During the process of conducting this systematic review, every attempt was made to avoid bias. By searching five different databases and grey literature, all possible efforts to identify all relevant studies were done, with no inappropriate exclusions of any study. However, it is possible that the databases searched did not include all of the published, unpublished, and ongoing studies, which might have resulted in

bias. A manual search was conducted, which may have contributed to limit the bias to some extent.

2.1.2. Limitations

In general, a limitation of this review might be the exclusion of articles published in languages other than French and English. However, research in medical sciences are usually translated in English, therefore it is less of a constraint.

Most studies included in this review were pilot studies, which is to be expected since the investigated topics are emerging areas of interest and preliminary studies constitute most of the available evidence.

For AI, the predominance of DTA single gate case-control design in included studies was considered a limitation since the AI models were only tested and validated on the original data set and were not tested on an external set, which limits the estimation of their performance. Only one study (Thanathornwong 2018) had a single gate cross-sectional design that involved testing on an external set of newly recruited patients whom their diagnostic was not known.

A limitation of some of the included AI studies, which by extension might be a limitation to this review, is the lack of precise reporting of unified conventional outcomes of DTA studies like accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and AUC, which did not allow to compare studies and populate a 2x2 contingency table. Only 5 studies had enough outcome reporting, which allowed to generate 2x2 contingency table. For nanotechnology and regenerative therapy, the methodological and clinical heterogeneity among studies only allowed a qualitative synthesis of the results. The methodological discrepancies across studies, such as sample sizes, intervention protocols, follow-up times, and outcome measures, might justify the heterogeneity of studies. Furthermore, several factors can affect the outcomes in these studies, namely age, physiological characteristics of intervention groups, expertise of clinicians and confounding factors.

Due to the lack of randomization in all CCTs of the included trials and the lack of details on the randomization procedure in many of the included studies, these

studies are prone to selection bias, demanding the conduct of further high-quality RCTs to limit bias and obtain more stable conclusions.

2.1.3. Strength points

A thorough and systematic searching process was used to ensure completeness and maximize external validity, as outlined in the 'Materials and methods' section of this systematic review. Five electronic databases and grey literature databases over the duration of more than 2 decades were searched. Moreover, a catch-up search was performed after 1 year of the initial search to ensure that this review stays up-to-date. As a result, this review included 28 studies with a total of 4791 participants which make for heavy material and valuable findings.

It was possible to conduct a meta-analysis on AI, which helped in getting concrete evidence on the performance of this technology in orthodontics at the current time. Throughout the screening and selection process, it was possible to identify some in vitro studies and finite element analysis that were highly relevant to researched subject. Their abstracts were carefully read to ensure that no relevant data was missed and to get a better understanding of the progress of research at early experimental stages in these interventions.

The included systematic reviews were assessed, and significantly pertinent and valuable data was received that was helpful in assimilating the topics that were supposed to be displayed in the process of making this systematic review.

2.2. Discussion and analysis of the included studies

2.2.1. Artificial intelligence

The field of orthodontics primarily deals with the diagnosis of malocclusion and planification of an organized, customized treatment. Malocclusion disrupts the occlusal function resulting in physiological problems and discomfort [54].

Treatment planning in orthodontics should maximize the benefits to the patient and minimize the associated risks. To better ensure a suitable treatment plan, there should be a rational decision-making process made through diagnostic tests and based on each patient's case. Even so, the 'perfect' treatment plan specific to

each patient is only relative, as reference standards in orthodontics are mainly executed by humans, and it is based on the experts' clinical experience. As a matter of facts, orthodontists' treatment plan can vary for a specific case [52]. The growing interest in artificial intelligence and data science in the technological communities, affected naturally many other fields especially the field of health sciences and consequently dentistry. The AI systems deal with computational based automated models that can think and act rationally. The AI-based models assist healthcare professionals in enhancing patient care. They can help clinicians operate more efficiently by saving time and suggesting therapeutic options that the practitioner had not considered.

In the context of precision orthodontics, these AI models can be customized with learning data sets specific to a subgroup of patients sharing the same characteristics (ethnicity, age, sex...) and thus, making customized expert systems to a set of individuals for decision-making and treatment planning.

This section of this review aims to discuss the performance and effectiveness of the AI models, identified in this review, that have been applied in orthodontic treatment planning and clinical decision making.

2.2.1.1. AI applications for orthodontic extractions planning

One of the major parts of an orthodontic treatment plan is judging if a specific case requires extractions, and in that case, the orthodontist should decide which teeth are to be extracted. Orthodontic extractions planning is of utmost importance, as extractions are irreversible and this decision, made at the earlier phases of the treatment, will dictate the outcome prognosis by having definitive consequences on the patient's final appearance and oral function. When confronted with much clinical variables and a large pool of extraction choices, the orthodontist's decision is based on the results of the diagnostic tests, which is then interpreted according to his clinical knowledge and experience [71]. In addition, as demonstrated in some of the included studies, there is a decision-making variability among the experts when confronted with the same cases.

This review, covering more than 2 decades of research, found that recently AI expert systems have been used on deciding the need for orthodontic extractions and the extraction patterns. 4 included studies covered this section, 3 studies used ANNs [40,48,91] and one study used ML neural network model and random forest ensemble classifier [77]. Only one study evaluated the need for extractions alone (Xie 2010) while other studies reported the detailed extraction diagnosis.

(Jung 2016) used ANNs in the diagnosis of extraction vs nonextraction, the decision-making success rate was 93% and the success rate of detailed diagnosis of the extraction patterns was 84%.

(Li 2019) also used ANNs to construct a model that offers several practicable alternatives for doctors to choose, which makes it more applicable. Accuracy of Extraction/no extraction was 94%. Accuracy of Extraction patterns was 84.2%, and accuracy of Anchorage patterns was 92.8% with a Sensitivity of 94.6%, Specificity of 93.8% and an AUC of 0.982 (95% CI 0.968–0.995). Li et al showed that the most important features for prediction of the ANN are “crowding, upper arch” “ANB” and “curve of Spee”.

(Suhail 2020) used machine learning (ML) neural network model and random forest ensemble classifier to determine extraction patterns. This model offers 2 treatment outcomes (primary and alternative). The expert’s agreement with the model on the primary outcome of therapy ranged from 65% to 71%, while agreement on either the primary or alternate outcome ranged from 93% to 98%.

(Xie 2010) used ANNs to diagnose the need for extractions. The model had an accuracy of 80% and showed that these indices “Anterior teeth uncovered by incompetent lips” and “IMPA (L1-MP)” were the two indices that gave the biggest contributions to the extraction decision. Sequentially, the index of FMA (FH-MP) gave the smallest contribution. All the AI models were effective and reliable.

The results obtained from these studies suggest that the AI expert systems can be useful for clinical decision making. ANN seems to be the most used AI model in orthodontic extractions planning. These pilot studies’ results are promising and suggest that there is more room for improving these models.

2.2.1.2. AI applications for orthognathic surgery planning

For patients who are too old for growth modification and who have dentofacial conditions that are too severe for surgical or orthodontic camouflage, orthognathic surgery to rearrange the maxilla, mandible, or chin, is the mainstay therapy [44]. Orthognathic surgery can drastically change appearance and occlusal function and thus, impacting the patient's sense of self and well-being. Like orthodontic extractions, surgery is irreversible, and its huge impacts should be assessed with care before carrying it out on the patient. In this context, this review included 4 studies that used ANNs, CNNs and ML algorithms.

(Choi 2019) used ANNs to determine surgery need and the associated extractions. The success rate of surgery/non-surgery diagnosis was 96%, and the final detailed success rate of surgery and extractions diagnosis was 91%.

(Lin 2020) used Machine learning (ML): Boruta method and XGBoost classifier for the evaluation of the need for orthognathic surgery in UCLP orthodontic patient. The ANB, PP-FH, CF, and facial convexity angle, indices were selected as predictive parameters of the future need for orthognathic surgery and had a 10-fold cross-validation accuracy of 87.4% with an F1-score of 0.714.

(Kim 2021) and (Shin 2021) used CNNs to diagnose the need for orthognathic surgery, both models were effective with high accuracies.

These models performed well in orthognathic surgery planning.

2.2.1.3. AI applications for deciding the need for orthodontic treatment and treatment planning

Throughout the decision-making process, orthodontists are usually confronted with many variables and indices and need to rely on heuristics to produce efficient decisions based on confounding and limited information. In practical situations distinguished by excessive aspects of variability and uncertainty, for instance, those experienced in orthodontics, cognitive biases and judgment errors related to heuristics are common. The current review assessed 3 studies in this area:

(Akçam 2002) used a fuzzy modelling system to select the appropriate types of headgear appliance for orthodontic patients. The average satisfaction rate of the examiners was 95.6%, and for 83 out of the 85 cases, it was 97.6%.

(Nieri 2010) In their retrospective cohort, applied Bayesian networks to evaluate the relative role and probable causal linkages among various factors influencing the diagnosis and treatment results of impacted maxillary canines. The bayesian network analysis was helpful in identifying possible correlations among the variables (bilateral impaction, the pre-treatment α -angle, age at start of treatment, d-distance, sex, and impaction site) considered for diagnosis and treatment of impacted canines.

(Thanathornwong 2018) used BNs to determine the need for orthodontic treatment. It showed an accuracy of 0.96, sensitivity of 0.95, specificity of 1.00 and an AUC of 0.91. The system delivered promising results; it showed a high degree of accuracy in classifying patients into groups needing and not needing orthodontic treatment. This study had a single-gate cross sectional design which involves applying the finalized AI diagnostic model on a new set of patients with unknown diagnosis and then evaluating its performance. This AI model succeeded in classifying the new patients and had a high degree of agreement with the two orthodontists, A (kappa value = 1.00) and B (kappa value = 0.894).

BNs seems to be the most suitable AI approach to deal with uncertainty and determine causal relationships between variables even in the case of missing clinical data. The results imply that these models may be used as a tool for less experienced orthodontists to predict the need for orthodontic treatment and treatment planning, as well as a useful tool for secondary opinion.

2.2.2. Nanotechnology

Nano-dentistry is the study of diagnosing, treating, and preventing oral and dental illnesses using nanostructured materials and technology. A common interest is to improve patients' oral health, decreasing the invasiveness of treatments and increasing compliance with doctors along with easing the global intervention [53].

These same interests can be applied in the field of orthodontics, which was the focus of the 8 studies included in this review.

In fact, these studies took interest into the antibacterial effects of some nanoparticles and their remineralization potential to prevent white spot lesions, reduce the number of cariogenic bacteria, and the effects of archwires' coating on surface roughness and topography. All studies had control groups.

2.2.2.1. White spot lesion extent and degree of enamel remineralization

Five studies [4,7,36,85,87] evaluated the effectiveness of nanoparticles in reducing white spot lesions and enamel remineralization. For the assessment of this outcome, most of the studies used fluorescence values (DIAGNOdent), and some used photography analysis, plaque index and/or enamel decalcification index (EDI) or naked eye method. Laser fluorescence seems to be the most objective outcome assessment used.

However, each of those studies used different interventions and different nanoparticles:

In fact, (Ali 2021) used nanosilver mouthwash and compared it to conventional chlorhexidine and fluoride mouthwashes.

(Badiee 2020) used nanohydroxyapatite toothpaste and compared it to a fluoride toothpaste.

(Jahanbin 2017) used a composite containing 5% nano amorphous calcium phosphate (NACP) to bond brackets.

(Venkatesan 2020) used titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticle for coating Ni-Ti archwires.

(Wang 2012) studied the effect of casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP) nanocomplexes in GC Tooth Mousse.

(Jahanbin 2017) and (Venkatesan 2020) evaluated both number of *S. mutans* and enamel mineral content, which are correlated to each other, as a reduced number of cariogenic bacteria usually results in prevention of enamel demineralization.

Although, (Venkatesan 2020) did not report any significant difference in enamel mineralization in the intervention group compared to the control group and concluded that orthodontic archwires appear to have a limited role in enamel demineralization, which is to be expected since archwires do not have direct contact with teeth surfaces.

On the other hand, all other studies reported statistically significant reduction in enamel demineralization ($P < 0.05$) with the use of nanoparticles. Bioactive nanoparticles seem to have a significant impact on white spot lesion extents which is correlated to their antibacterial properties and their infiltration potential into enamel rods thanks to their small size.

2.2.2.2. Number of *S. mutans*, Planktonic growth and biofilm formation of cariogenic bacteria

Four studies [26,29,36,85] evaluated the antibacterial effectiveness of nanoparticles.

For the assessment of this outcome, 2 studies used real-time PCR and the other 2 used digital colony counters.

(Farhadian 2016) incorporated silver nanoparticles into removable retainers.

(Ghorbanzadeh 2015) also used silver nanoparticles to study the effects of baseplates with in situ generated NanoAg and baseplates incorporated with NanoAg on cariogenic bacteria.

While (Jahanbin 2017) used a composite containing 5% nano amorphous calcium phosphate (NACP) to bond brackets.

And (Venkatesan 2020) used titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticle for coating Ni-Ti archwires.

All studies found a reduced number of cariogenic bacteria especially *S. mutans* in the intervention groups compared to the control groups. This difference was statistically significant in each study. These findings accentuate the effectiveness of some specific bioactive nanoparticles on inhibition of bacterial growth around orthodontic appliances (retainers, baseplates, brackets, and archwires). Silver

nanoparticles were used in 2 studies [26,29] and the findings were comparable, which emphasises on the antibacterial effects of this specific nanoparticle.

2.2.2.3. Surface roughness and surface topography

A reduced surface roughness and a uniform smooth surface topography in archwires during orthodontic treatment are important since it reduces frictional forces and diminishes bacterial adhesion.

Only 1 study (Venkatesan 2020) investigated surface topography and roughness of orthodontic archwires after TiO₂ nanoparticles coating. For this outcome assessment, 3-dimensional surface profilometry and scanning electron microscopy were used [85].

The surface roughness (Ra) of the control group at T₀ was greater than the Ra of TiO₂ nanoparticle coated NiTi wires ($P = 0.0005$). After 1 month, both groups had increased surface roughness, though the control group wires showed higher roughness in comparison with nano TiO₂ coated wires but it was not statistically significant ($P = 0.309$). The surface topography of TiO₂ nanoparticle coated NiTi wires showed a uniform smooth layer of coating at T₀, but after 1 month, delamination and deterioration of the coating were observed. The coating thickness of the TiO₂ nanoparticle coated NiTi wires decreased by 32.45 nm which was statistically significant ($P < 0.001$).

Although TiO₂ nanoparticle coating on NiTi archwires results in an initial reduction in roughness, after 1 month of intra-oral use, the smoothness was lost and the coating thickness was reduced by 60% along with its deterioration and delamination. These findings suggest that TiO₂ nanoparticle coating was not the best approach to reduce friction and improving surface roughness and topography. De Stefani et al. [16] concluded that the best nanomaterials for achieving the goal of friction reduction are MoS₂ (molybdenum disulfide) and W₂ (tungsten disulfide). And for bacterial reduction, they recommended TiO₂ nanoparticles doped with nitrogen or Ag-Zr nanocomposite coatings.

2.2.2.4. Periodontal assessment of treatment-induced gingivitis

Only one study (Alam 2021) [3] assessed the plaque index (PI), papillary bleeding gingival index (PBI), probing depth (PD), and clinical attachment loss (CAL) after application of Nano-bio fusion gingival gel on the experimental side, twice a day after brushing for 90 days. This nanoparticle-containing gel acts through its fast absorption by the gingival tissues thanks to its small particles size. Alam et al. showed that from baseline to the seventh day to the 90th day, the treatment group showed significant improvement in PI, PBI, and PD over time compared with the placebo group ($P < 0.001$). So, NFBFG demonstrated a beneficial clinical effect in a relatively short period. NFBFG, with its own beneficial modalities, allows us to advocate in the management of fixed orthodontic treatment induced gingivitis.

2.2.3. Regenerative therapy (Stem cells / PRF)

Regenerative dentistry is a new field of research that uses tissues' self-healing and regenerative potentials. More successful dental therapy is possible with the use of bone and bone substitutes, membranes, growth factors, stem cells, platelet concentrates, and a combination of the mentioned cells and tissues [37].

2.2.3.1. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF)

The second generation of platelet concentrate, platelet rich fibrin (PRF), was initially depicted by French scientist Choukroun in 2000. It is obtained by centrifuging the blood of patients without anticoagulant or other biochemical modifications. PRF has a dense fibrin network with leukocytes, cytokines, structural glycoproteins, and growth factors [19].

2.2.3.1.1. Periodontal effects and hard tissue reconstruction of alveolar bone

Three studies [15,31,61] assessed hard tissue reconstruction of alveolar bone using CBCT scan and/or evaluated periodontal effects of PRF.

(Dayoub 2019) showed that PRF increased gingival thickness and was successful in changing the thin gingival biotype into thick biotype, but there was no significant

difference in the width of keratinized gingiva in PRF group and control group ($P>0.05$).

(Gonen 2019) compared various corticotomy assisted rapid orthodontics techniques (conventional, with bone graft, with PRF). The study showed that PRF combination with corticotomy was efficient in preserving the width of keratinized gingiva and providing bone thickness compared to corticotomy alone.

(Nemtoi 2018) showed that PRF was useful for socket preservation after extractions. There was a high correlation between bone quality and socket augmentation with PRF. The effect of PRF on periodontal tissues and alveolar preservation seem promising but not conclusive. There is the need for more extensive research in this area.

2.2.3.1.2. Tooth Movement and Post-Orthodontic Stability

Three trials [61,70 ,81] evaluated the effect of L-PRF or PRF on orthodontic tooth movement.

(Pacheco 2020) [70] measured the rate of maxillary canines distalization and inclination which reflects the rate of OTM. (Nemtoi 2018) [61] (Tehranchi 2018) [64] Both studies found that using these platelets' derivatives in the extraction socket can speed up orthodontic tooth movement ($p = 0.006$), and Tehranchi et al. found that there was no statistical difference in OTM rate between teeth in the maxillary and mandibular arch. On the other hand, (Pacheco 2020) showed that the rate of distalization and inclination of the canines were greater in the control side than the L-PRF side ($P<0.05$) meaning that the use of L-PRF decreased the rate of OTM of the maxillary canines in young adults.

(Gonen 2019) found out that the duration of orthodontic treatment was decreased in all corticotomy groups, which does not give information on the specific effect of associating PRF with corticotomy on the duration of treatment.

The study by (Muñoz 2016) [60] used a Wicklo's modified periodontally accelerated osteogenic orthodontics (PAOO) technique with L-PRF incorporated into the graft and as covering membrane. It was the only study that evaluated the effects of L-PRF considering inflammation and post-orthodontic stability. They

demonstrated that, in a high percentage of patients (72.7%), edema resolution was set about day 4, and average treatment time was 9.3 months with an orthodontic stability that was preserved for two or more years post-surgery in all patients.

Before the (Pacheco 2020) study, Nemtoi et al, Tehranchi et al, and Francisco et al in their SR [27], concluded that PRF may shorten orthodontic treatment time. But now with the study of Pacheco et al, there is the need for reassessment and conducting more trials with elimination of confounding factors.

2.2.3.2. Stem cells (SC)

Stem cells are a type of cell that can regenerate and develop into different types of cells [37].

The use of stem cells in orthodontics is still experimental and far from mainstream. The results of this study suggest that stem cells and regenerative therapies can help orthodontists execute their jobs more efficiently.

This review included only one study (Mazzetti 2018) that used stem cells on orthodontic cleft lip and palate patients. These patients were submitted to orthopedic treatment with palatal device since their birth, and after primary lip and palate surgery stem cells were injected into the surgical wound [56].

Lip soft tissue inflammatory process in first 48h, lip transitory hypertrophic scar, palatal dehiscence, palatal fistula, and fibrosis between soft and hard palate at the second surgical time were assessed subjectively, but the differences between intervention and control groups were statistically significant. At the second palatal surgery, the SCG had a less inflammatory response in the soft tissue of the lip, less scar hypertrophy, no palate fistula or dehiscence, and less fibrosis between the hard and soft palate. In cleft lip and palate surgery, stem cells reduce inflammation and develop better scars than the regular series. The study did not observe any bone neoformation after 2 years postoperative which can be attributed to the low number of stem cells used and the non-association of SC with other growth factors or regenerative procedures (PRP/Bone morphogenic protein-2).

Stem cells use in cleft lip and palate patients seems propitious which calls for the need of more well-designed multi-center controlled cohorts and RCTs with more sample size and objective outcome measures.

2.2.4. Quantitative synthesis analysis:

The quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) included 5 articles: (Kim 2021), (Li 2019), (Lin 2020), (Shin 2021), and (Thanathornwong 2018). All the studies were DTA single gate case-controls apart from 1 study [82] that had a cross sectional design, but this did not have much influence as the original internal dataset used for making the AI system was included in the meta-analysis. Thus, all studies were considered case-controls.

(Lin 2020), (Shin 2021), and (Thanathornwong 2018) had low risk of bias. While the other two had moderate risk of bias.

(Kim 2021) used CNNs, (Li 2019) ANNs, (Lin 2020) ML algorithms, (Shin 2021) CNNs, and (Thanathornwong 2018) BNs. Since CNNs is just one kind of ANNs, then 3 studies were using ANNs and two studies using BNs and ML algorithms, which can be considered as a source of heterogeneity.

Kim et al. made a CNN model for orthognathic surgery planning using cephalograms as datasets and compared the performance with 1 orthodontist. The study reported AUC, accuracy, Sp, and Se.

Li et al. used ANNs for extraction planning using medical records including cephalograms, compared it with 2 orthodontists having experience between 26 and 12 years. The study reported: accuracy, AUC, Se, and Sp.

Lin et al. used the Boruta method and XGBoost classifier for orthognathic surgery planning using cephalograms, compared it to 2 specialists and reported as outcomes: accuracy, Se, Sp, F1-score, and a 2-by-2 confusion matrix.

Shin et al. used CNNs for orthognathic surgery planning using cephalograms and compared it to 6 specialists. The study reported accuracy, Se, Sp, and 2-by-2 table.

Thanathornwong used BNs for orthodontic treatment needs using impressions and photographs and compared it to 2 orthodontists reporting accuracy, Se, Sp, and AUC. There are noticeable sources of heterogeneity between studies such as

the study factor, modality, and AI approach. Also, the reference standard comparison was not consistent across studies (the number and experience of evaluators were not always reported and were varying between studies).

In the ideal case, a meta-regression and sub-group analysis would be conducted due to the present variations that induce substantial heterogeneity, but only a small pool of studies was available. The goal was to have a global view on the performance of the developed AI models in the orthodontic field especially in treatment planning and decision-making. The pooled sensitivity and specificity were 0.965 (95% CI 0.921-0.985), 0.962 (95% CI 0.878-0.989) respectively, with an AUC of 0.99 (95% CI 0.98 - 1.00) and an accuracy that reached 95.47%.

PLR was 25.304 (95% CI 7.686-83.310) >5 and the NLR was 0.036 (95% CI 0.016-0.081) <0.2, which indicates a clinically useful test and strong diagnostic evidence. These measures indicate high performance despite the clear limitations in the studies included. Thus, it can only be concluded that AI models were successful in predicting valid treatment plans and accurate decisions. These models can be further improved for more applicable consistent results. The impact of this technology in the orthodontic field is clear as there is much potential in this emerging technology and its medical uses. The current systematic review and meta-analysis-DTA had several limitations; like the small number of literature studies with adequate and complete statistical information sets, including TP, TN, FP, and FN as well as accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. And, the substantial heterogeneity and variability among studies.

2.3. Agreements and disagreements with other reviews

This review identified 2 systematic reviews: 1 in AI (Khanagar 2020) [43] and another one in PRF (Francisco 2020) [27]. Both reviews were recent qualitative reviews and had a good methodological quality.

(Khanagar 2020) aimed to document the scope and performance of the artificial intelligence-based models that have been widely used in orthodontic diagnosis, treatment planning, and predicting the prognosis [43]. This study included articles that used AI for: automatic identification of cephalometric landmarks, determining

need for extraction, determining the degree of maturation of the cervical vertebra, predicting attractiveness after orthognathic surgery, and predicting the need for orthodontic treatment. The review assessed the AI models analysed as effective and concluded these systems can be of great value in orthodontics.

In contrast to this review, only AI models that had a direct clinical significance and effects on the treatment outcome during the treatment planning and decision-making phases were included. (Khanagar 2020) included 16 studies of which 5 were included in this review as well (Xie 2010, Jung 2016, Choi 2019, Thanathornwong 2018, and Li 2019).

(Francisco 2020) aimed to investigate the applications and effects of PRF in orthodontics. The included studies assessed; alveolar cleft reconstruction in alveolar cleft patients, and tooth movement and post-orthodontic stability.

All 3 articles analysed in the tooth movement section of Francisco et al.'s review were included in this SR. On the other hand, for alveolar cleft reconstruction, the articles included in Francisco review did not appear in the search results but were read and analysed. These articles included alveolar cleft patients which did not meet the inclusion criteria, since the population had to be orthodontic patients meaning that participants should have received an orthodontic or orthopedic treatment of any sort at some point of their global treatment. Therefore, these articles did not qualify for inclusion in this review. But their findings were still taken into consideration.

(Francisco 2020) concluded that PRF can improve alveolar cleft reconstruction and it may shorten the orthodontic treatment time, thereby reducing associated costs. Disagreements concerning the effect of PRF on orthodontic tooth movement were found, since this review included a study that opposes the findings of the previous studies (Pacheco 2020) which makes the effects of PRF highly debatable.

2.5. Author's conclusions

2.5.1. Recommendations for clinicians

The findings of this scientific review did not present sufficient evidence for clinical practice recommendations. As specified earlier, most of the included studies were pilot preliminary studies and even with the synthesis of all studies' results, drawing conclusions related to the daily orthodontic practice was not possible. This was mostly due to the heterogeneity of the interventions and the varying protocols and outcome measures.

However, thanks to the extensive bibliography included in this analysis, it was possible to provide credible suggestions for practice:

- In the phase of orthodontic treatment planning, clinicians are encouraged to consult each other's opinions and take decisions as a team of experts. This reduces the decision-making variability among the experts when confronted with the same cases as demonstrated in this review.
- Amongst the most widely used nanoparticles for enamel remineralization, nanohydroxyapatite toothpaste and CPP-ACP nanocomplexes are well-studied in the field of conservative and preventive dentistry and are commercialized since much. Their effects on remineralizing early enamel lesions are proven. Orthodontists can prescribe them for their patients to prevent or reduce white spot lesions associated with orthodontic treatment.
- Corticotomy assisted rapid orthodontics or PAOO is demonstrated to accelerate the orthodontic treatment duration, and the use of PRF is safe, cheap, and effective in easing the side effects of this procedure.
- Practitioners have to rely on their clinical experience and take the circumstances and conditions of each patient into conscientious consideration.

2.5.2. Recommendations for future research

For artificial intelligence:

- The methodological quality of DTA studies should be improved by reducing potential sources of bias in their conduct, like; sampling and recruitment methods (consecutive, random), study design (case controls should be avoided), and inappropriate exclusions.
- More DTA single-gate cross sectional design studies should be performed.
- Adequate reporting of reference standards description and reference test criteria for positive test along with appropriate description of index tests and criteria of positive test are desired.
- Studies should report thresholds, cut-off values, and conventional DTA outcome measures (Accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, AUC) along with 2-by-2 tables.
- To assess clinical effectiveness and the practical utility of AI models as diagnostic tests compared to the conventional reference standards, diagnostic test randomised controlled trials (D-RCTs) should be carried.
- Researchers are encouraged to publish the code of AI systems used as open source, so other researchers can work on improving the existing models and collaborate to enhance the system's accuracy and applicability.

For nanotechnology:

During the database search and study selection, a number of noteworthy in-vitro and animal studies about nanotechnology could be identified. These studies were promising and suggest huge impact if proven in human trials. In fact, De Stefani et al. [16] presented the major findings of in-vitro and animal studies concerning applications of nanotechnology in orthodontic elastomeric ligatures, orthodontic power chains, orthodontic bands, orthodontic miniscrews, control of oral biofilm, coated orthodontic archwires. These applications are promising and interesting, thus the researchers should focus on:

- Conducting more human clinical trials based on the in-vitro and animal trials findings.
- Improving the quality of RCTs, CCTs.

For Regenerative therapy (PRF/Stem cells):

Due to the heterogeneity present in the included studies concerning outcome measures and preparation protocols, future research needs to focus on:

- Developing unified protocols for PRF and SC preparation and applications.
- Conducting multi-center RCTs with unified protocols and bigger sample sizes along with high quality, controlled, cohorts with long follow-up times.
- Using objective outcome measures for the assessment of outcomes.
- Reporting uniform and clearer variables.

In the process of designing clinical trials, important parameters have to be taken into consideration:

- Explicit exclusion and inclusion criteria must be defined.
- All age ranges have to be involved in the study to expand the results' generalizability.
- Multi-center trials have to be conducted in all parts of the world.
- Preliminary sample size calculations have to be undertaken, while considering the clustering of teeth within the mouth.
- New technologies, materials, and techniques have to be instigated in human trials to hasten the development in the reviewed fields.
- Treatment protocols and follow-up periods, have to be as identical as possible among studies and must be seemingly reported.
- Clinician feedback, time-efficiency, participant contentment, and viability with distinct nanoparticles or regenerative techniques have to be mentioned.

Conclusion

Conclusion

In this era, precision orthodontics is no longer a far-fetched goal as each day we strive closer to precise customized healthcare. Various therapies and technologies have been developed and are still being harnessed to satisfy this concept. Among those emerging interventions, particular interest was taken into artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapies.

We were able to analyse and synthesise all relevant research of the past two decades, and we assessed the evidence on the use of artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapy in planning and delivering a customized orthodontic treatment. This review accentuates the undebatable impact of those reviewed interventions as it is clear now how much potential they behold.

The exponential development of computational technologies portends consequent breakthroughs in healthcare AI expert systems, especially in orthodontics. As shown in this review and other recent reviews, AI technology is able to ameliorate the diagnostic reliability and precision for orthodontic treatments, therewith assisting the clinicians in operating more accurately and efficiently.

The multitude of different interventions in nanotechnology and regenerative therapy show that despite the present heterogeneity among studies, there is still much room for improvements and research as most included studies were pilot preliminary studies. We speculate that in the years to come, each outcome of the studies assessed in this review will be further investigated and developed.

These therapies and technologies can ease the global treatment and improve outcomes as previously shown. Our findings encourage the further development in AI, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapies fields research.

But still, there is yet no practical recommendations for daily orthodontic practice as the studied interventions are still in the experimental phase and the evidence is scarce. Thus, the clinicians cannot fully adapt them in their clinical situations and

therefore, still have to adhere to the conventional treatments while taking into consideration our recommendations.

More high-quality studies are required to acquire deeper insights into these interventions since a finer comprehension of the benefits and drawbacks of each therapy, technique and technology and their comparison could usher to more evidence-based, effective, and cost-efficient treatments. Future studies are warranted to further assess the clinical significance of artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapies.

Monastir, on. 08/02/2022

Opinion of the director of the thesis

Supervisor

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Appendices

APPENDICES

Appendix 1-A: Search strategy in electronic databases.

Appendix 1-B: Search strategy results in electronic databases.

Appendix 2: Customised data collection form.

Appendix 3: Risk of bias assessment JBI checklists.

Appendix 4: Oxford Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine 2011 Levels of Evidence.

Appendix 5: GRADE recommendations.

Appendix 6: DTA studies designs and outcome measures.

Appendix 7: PRISMA 2020 Main Checklist.

All the appendices used in this review are available online as supplementary materials at the **Zenodo** open-access repository:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5938522>

Jihed M'HAMED***The future of precision orthodontics: Integration of technology and biomedicine into customized therapy******L'avenir de l'orthodontie de précision : intégration de la technologie et de la biomédecine dans une thérapie personnalisée***

2nd Cycle Thesis – Dental Medicine – Monastir**106 Pages - 22 Figures - 08 Tables****Abstract:**

Introduction: Artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapy are the principal catalysts for achieving precision orthodontics. Advances in these fields directly impact the clinical practice.

Objective: This systematic review aimed to assess available evidence on the use of artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapy in the planning and delivery of customized orthodontic therapy. The aim of the meta-analysis was to evaluate the performance and effectiveness of AI models for orthodontic treatment planning and decision-making.

Materials and methods: PubMed, EBSCO host, ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Web of Science were searched over the period from January 1, 2000 to January 9, 2021, then they were updated until January 19, 2022. A systematic review and diagnostic test accuracy meta-analysis were performed.

Results: Overall, 2137 records were identified. A total of twenty-eight studies were ultimately included in the qualitative synthesis, of which five AI studies were included in the meta-analysis. The effectiveness of each intervention was assessed through comparison of the evidence supporting their use. Pooled sensitivity, specificity, diagnostic odds ratio (DOR), and area under the curve (AUC) with 95% CI of AI models' performance were: 0.965 (0.921-0.985), 0.962 (0.878-0.989), 695.537 (232.742-2078.572), 0.99 (0.98-1.00), respectively. The accuracy of AI systems reached 95.47%.

Conclusion: Artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, and regenerative therapy have a notable impact on contemporary orthodontic therapy and will shape the future of precision orthodontics. These interventions can ease global treatment and improve outcomes. AI models are successful in predicting valid treatment plans with accurate decisions. Nevertheless, there is a critical need for further studies in each intervention with adequate methodologies.

Résumé :

Introduction: L'intelligence artificielle, la nanotechnologie et la thérapie régénérative sont les principaux catalyseurs de l'orthodontie de précision. Les progrès dans ces domaines ont un impact direct sur la pratique clinique.

Objectif: Le but de cette revue systématique était d'évaluer les données probantes disponibles sur l'utilisation de l'intelligence artificielle, de la nanotechnologie et de la thérapie régénérative dans la planification et la prestation d'une thérapie orthodontique personnalisée. La méta-analyse avait pour objectif d'évaluer le rendement et l'efficacité des modèles d'IA pour la planification des traitements orthodontiques et la prise de décision.

Matériel et méthodes: PubMed, EBSCO host, ScienceDirect, Scopus et Web of Science ont été recherchés pour la période du 1er janvier 2000 au 9 janvier 2021, puis mis à jour jusqu'au 19 janvier 2022. Une revue systématique et une méta-analyse des tests diagnostiques ont été réalisées.

Résultats: Globalement, 2,137 références ont été identifiées. Vingt-huit études ont été incluses dans la synthèse qualitative, dont cinq études sur l'IA ont été incluses dans la méta-analyse. L'efficacité de chaque intervention a été évaluée en comparant les données probantes à l'appui de leur utilisation. La sensibilité, la spécificité, le Diagnostic odds ratio (DOR) et l'aire sous la courbe avec un IC à 95 % de la performance des modèles d'IA étaient : 0,965 (0,921-0,985), 0,962 (0,878-0,989), 695,537 (232,742-2078,572), 0,99 (0,98-1,00), respectivement. La précision des systèmes d'IA a atteint 95,47 %.

Conclusion: L'intelligence artificielle, la nanotechnologie et la thérapie régénérative ont un impact notable sur la thérapie orthodontique contemporaine et façonneront l'avenir de l'orthodontie de précision. Ces interventions peuvent faciliter le traitement global et améliorer les résultats. Les modèles d'IA ont réussi à prédire des plans de traitement valides avec des décisions précises. Néanmoins, il existe un besoin critique d'études supplémentaires dans chaque intervention avec des méthodologies adéquates.

Column of classification : Dentofacial orthopedics**Rubrique de classement :** Orthopédie dentofaciale

Keywords: Orthodontics, Technology, Biomedicine, Precision, Nanotechnology, Artificial intelligence, Regenerative therapy, Stem cells, Platelet-rich fibrin.

Mots clés : Orthodontie, Technologie, Biomédecine, Précision, Nanotechnologie, Intelligence artificielle, Thérapie régénérative, Cellules souches, Fibrine riche en plaquettes.

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